

BIOBUILD

Thermal Solutions for Green Buildings

Deliverable D3.1

Report on optimal conditions for plant oil-based binders (curability, polymerization technology and processability)

Due Date:	December 2025
Submission Date:	26 December 2025
Dissemination level:	PUBLIC
Lead Beneficiary:	SLU
Lead Authors:	Sajjad Ghodrati, Meysam Nazari, Nasko Terziev
Project Acronym: BIOBUILD	Project Number: 101135629
Start Date of Project: 01/01/2024	End Date of Project: 31/12/2027

Disclaimer

The designations employed and the presentation material in this information product (Deliverable) do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the BIOBUILD Consortium. The mention of specific companies, events, products of manufacturers, do not imply that these have been endorsed or recommended by the BIOBUILD Consortium.

The views expressed in this Deliverable are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the BIOBUILD Consortium.

Third Party materials: Users wishing to reuse material from this work that is attributed to a third party, such as tables, figures, etc., are responsible for determining whether permission is needed for that reuse and for obtaining permission from the copyright holder. The risk of claims resulting from infringement of any third-party-owned component in the work rests solely with the user.

Document Control Information	
Title	D3.1 Report on optimal conditions for plant oil-based binders (curability, polymerization technology and processability)
Editor	Meysam Nazari, Nasko Terziev
Contributors	Sajjad Ghodrati, Meysam Nazari, Nasko Terziev
Reviewer(s)	Meysam Nazari, Sebastian Gritsch, Nasko Terziev
Dissemination Level (please choose just one according to the DoA)	<input type="checkbox"/> SEN - Sensitive (please provide one-page Publishable Summary) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public
Approved by (please tick the boxes after all the partners have provided their written approval of the deliverable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SLU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ASRO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BOKU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CNR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> COAC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SQIM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pervanovo Invest <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PCMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RTDS Association <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UDL <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UNIPD
Underlying IPRs	Are there intellectual property rights included in this deliverable? Yes
Underlying Datasets	Are there relevant datasets included in this deliverable? Yes

Table of contents

Summary	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Vegetable oils as bio-binders.....	6
2.1 Criteria for selecting the appropriate EVOs.....	9
2.2 Strategies for achieving optimal thermosets from ELO.....	10
3. Examining the performance of homopolymerization catalysts.....	11
3.1 Sample preparation with aluminum trifluoromethanesulfonate and tris(pentafluorophenyl)borane catalysts	11
3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).....	12
3.3 Selection of an appropriate catalyst concentration	14
3.4 Mechanical properties of thermosets	15
3.5 Processing of wood composites with Al(OTf) ₃ catalyst.....	16
4. Incorporating aromatic rings into the thermoset binder structure	17
4.1 Diphenylamine.....	17
4.2 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid.....	18
5. Application of small multifunctional hardeners	20
5.1 Maleic anhydride	20
5.2 Citric acid.....	21
5.2.1 Differential scanning calorimetry and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy.....	23
5.2.2 Mechanical properties and thermal resistance of thermosets with citric acid	25
5.2.3 Processing of wood composites with citric acid as hardener	27
5.3 Oxalic acid.....	31
5.3.1 Differential scanning calorimetry and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy.....	31
5.3.2 Mechanical properties and thermal resistance of thermosets with oxalic acid.....	34
5.3.3 Processing of wood composites with oxalic acid as hardener	35
6. Properties of wood composites with citric and oxalic acids as hardeners	36
6.1 Physical-mechanical properties	36
6.2 Thermal properties	37
7. Curing of ELO by UV photo-polymerization	39
7.1 UV-curing based on free-radical polymerization	40
7.2 UV-curing based on cationic polymerization	41
8. Conclusions and recommendations for pilot-plant upscaling	44
References	45
List of Figures	48
List of Tables.....	50
Appendix	51

Summary

The objectives of Task 3.1 were to select a plant oil and find the optimal conditions for cationic polymerization of the epoxidized oil catalysed by either Lewis acids or dicarboxylic acid hardeners working at low temperature; the above options were used as plant oil-based binders for the composites (or wallboards) with ethyl palmitate as bioPCM. Photo-polymerization of the epoxidized oil by UV curing was also studied. Catalysts and hardeners were studied and evaluated based on several criteria, including bio-based content, curing time and temperature, physical-mechanical, thermal properties and cost. It was found that citric and oxalic acids fulfil best the requirements. The two acids were selected as hardeners for producing bioPCM-containing composites at a pilot scale (see Deliverable D4.3 “Demonstration of wallboard production”).

Preliminary physical-mechanical results demonstrated that oxalic acid is better hardener than citric acid. Addition of impregnated particles decreases the mechanical properties due to insufficient adhesion between the binder and particles with oily surfaces. Another advantage of using oxalic acid is that the curing temperature is 60°C. Stability of the impregnated ethyl palmitate is good; no leaching was observed after 30 days' exposure at 50°C temperature. However, crystallization of ethyl palmitate on the board's surface must be eliminated. Crystallization does not mean leaching of the bioPCM, it is a surface phenomenon that is an aesthetic problem and probably can influence the finishing of the boards by lamination or painting. In order to eliminate crystallization of bioPCM, UV-curable coatings were formulated with ELO and either triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) or bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate to enable low-temperature curing. Working temperature of the bioPCM-wood composites with oxalic and a melting enthalpy of ca. 70 J/g justified the use of oxalic acid as hardener to improve the thermal performance of the composite. Additionally, processing the composite at lower curing temperature than citric acid facilitated the technology of the product.

Following the laboratory results, SLU prepared the coming work in WP4 where the scale-up of the composite production demands ca. 180 kg ELO binder, provided with guidelines and safety instructions. SLU has collaborated with the project partner BOKU by exchange of experience in analytical analyses and characterization of the composite binders. The results of Task 3.1, presented in Deliverable 3.1, are conveyed and used further in Task 3.4 in WP3 and Tasks 4.1-4.4 in the work of WP4.

1. Introduction

Deliverable 3.1 “*Report on optimal conditions for plant oil-based binders (curability, polymerization technology and processability)*” is a part of WP3 and based on the work in Task 3.1 “*Fast- and low temperature curing plant oil-based binders*”. The overall objective of WP3 is to upscale the production of three binders for wood fibres hosting bioPCM-reinforced composites and, specifically, to optimize the production of plant oil-based binder in Task 3.1. The specific objectives in Task 3.1 were as follows and the results are reported in the present Deliverable 3.1.

- *Optimal conditions for cationic polymerization of epoxidized plant oils catalysed by a Lewis acid tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borane at low temperatures;*
- *Fast curing plant oil-based binders through photo-polymerization and in-situ UV curing;*
- *Synthesis of biobased dicarboxylic acid type hardener for low temperature curing of plant oil-based binders;*
- *Analytical analysis and characterisation by in-situ FTIR, DSC, 1H NMR and 13C NMR, TGA, DMA, tensile tests, shore tests, and solubility tests;*
- *Scale-up of plant oil-based binders: following lab synthesis, study the scale-up of the production of plant oil-based binders up to 10 kg/batch, providing guidelines and safety procedures.*

2. Vegetable oils as bio-binders

Today, the majority of industrial polymers are produced from non-renewable feedstocks and consume roughly 7% of the global oil and gas supply [1, 2]. As fossil resources decline, energy prices vary, and environmental pressures intensify, finding sustainable, renewable substitutes for conventional petroleum-based polymers has become increasingly important.

Biopolymer materials made from biological sources are gaining significant interest as alternatives to traditional petroleum-based plastics. Their appeal comes from features such as being derived from renewable resources, their capacity to biodegrade in many cases, and their generally reduced environmental footprint over their full life span.

The main renewable resources used to produce biopolymers include vegetable oils, various polysaccharides such as cellulose and starch, phenolic and polyphenolic substances, and different types of proteins [3]. Among these options, vegetable oils stand out as especially attractive building blocks for sustainable polymers because they are widely available, naturally biodegradable, and exhibit low toxicity. In addition, polymers made from vegetable oils possess several practical advantages over those derived from carbohydrates or proteins, making them easier to process and apply in various fields [1, 4]:

- While vegetable oils do not occur in polymeric form on their own, they serve as valuable starting materials for producing monomers that can be converted into a wide range of polymers, such as polyurethanes, polyesters, polyethers (epoxides), and polyolefins. This versatility makes it possible to easily tune their structures.
- Vegetable oils are suitable for the synthesis of hydrophobic polymers and serve as a useful counterpart to more hydrophilic bio-based materials such as carbohydrates and proteins.
- Vegetable oils can be transformed into monomers that closely resemble those derived from petroleum. As a result, polymers made from vegetable oils can serve as effective substitutes for conventional petroleum-based polymers, offering comparable performance.

Because triglycerides contain predominantly aliphatic chains, materials derived from them often lack the stiffness and mechanical strength needed for certain demanding applications.

Vegetable oils, obtained from a wide range of plant sources and commonly identified by their origin, such as soybean, palm, or linseed, are composed primarily of triglycerides. These triglycerides are esters formed from glycerol combined with different fatty acids (Figure 1).

Figure 1. General structure of the vegetable oils (R_1 , R_2 , R_3 are aliphatic chains of different fatty acids) [1, 5].

Fatty acids are typically long, unbranched chains containing an even number of carbon atoms, and they differ in how many double bonds they contain. Some fatty acids, however, ricinoleic acid for example, has extra functional groups such as hydroxyl groups [6] (Table 1).

Table 1. Chemical structure and closed formula of some key fatty acids [5, 7].

Fatty acid name	Chemical structure	Closed formula
Palmitic		$C_{16}H_{32}O_2$
Stearic		$C_{18}H_{36}O_2$
Oleic		$C_{18}H_{34}O_2$
Linoleic		$C_{18}H_{32}O_2$
Linolenic		$C_{18}H_{30}O_2$
Ricinoleic		$C_{18}H_{34}O_3$

In addition, the fatty acid types and amount in a vegetable oil depends on factors such as the plant species and the conditions in which it is grown, and its physical and chemical behaviour is strongly shaped by how unsaturated those fatty acids are. For example, linseed oil is rich in linoleic, linolenic, and oleic acids, while castor oil is dominated by ricinoleic acid, whose extra hydroxyl group enhances its reactivity [8] (Table 2).

Table 2. Fatty acid names and compositions of common vegetable oils [1, 6].

Vegetable oil name	Average number of Double bonds per triglyceride	Fatty acid percentage				
		Palmitic	Stearic	Oleic	Linoleic	Linolenic
Palm	1.7	42.8	4.2	40.5	10.1	—
Olive	2.8	13.7	2.5	71.1	10.0	0.6
Sesame	3.9	9.0	6.0	41.0	43.0	1.0
Corn	4.5	10.9	2.0	25.4	59.6	1.2
Soybean	4.6	11.0	4.0	23.4	53.3	7.8
Sunflower	4.7	5.2	2.7	37.2	53.8	1.0
Linseed	6.6	5.5	3.5	19.1	15.3	56.6

Over the past decades, numerous polymeric materials derived from vegetable oils have been developed. Unmodified vegetable oils have been employed to create bio-renewable polymers through thermal or cationic polymerization, utilizing the C=C bonds present in their fatty acid chains [9].

Chemically modified vegetable oils, such as those containing epoxide groups, show enhanced reactivity and can participate in ring-opening polymerization to generate thermosetting materials with strong thermal and

mechanical performance. Another important group of monomers derived from vegetable oils are polyols, which can react with diisocyanates to produce polyurethanes or with carboxylic acids to yield polyesters; these materials are widely used in products like coatings, adhesives, and foams [10-12]. Figure 2 presents typical reaction pathways and the key raw materials involved in synthesizing several major types of biopolymers.

Figure 2. General forms of reaction routes and raw materials used in the production of most common biopolymers.

Polyesters represent one of the most widely used classes of polymers, and numerous structures with diverse properties have been produced using vegetable oils as starting materials. For example, polyester resins can be obtained through condensation reactions between monoglycerides derived from vegetable oils and various anhydrides or carboxylic acids. They can also be formed by curing epoxidized vegetable oils (EVOs) with different acids or anhydrides, either without catalysts or in the presence of catalysts such as tertiary amines, including imidazoles [13-16].

The characteristics of the polyester thermosets produced are influenced by several factors, including the specific carboxylic acids or anhydrides used, the molar ratio between these reagents and the epoxy groups, and the overall epoxy functionality of the system. In general, acids or anhydrides with more rigid molecular frameworks, such as phthalic anhydride and hexahydrophthalic anhydride (Figure 3), tend to produce materials with higher glass transition temperatures.

Figure 3. Chemical structure of phthalic anhydride and hexahydrophthalic anhydride.

Epoxy resins form a major family of thermosetting polymers. They are produced from precursor molecules that contain epoxy, or oxirane, functional groups. When these groups react with suitable catalysts or curing agents, they form cross-linked networks that offer strong mechanical performance, high chemical resistance, and good adhesion, making them useful in a wide range of applications. At present, epoxy resins derived from bisphenol A (BPA) and epichlorohydrin represent roughly 80-85% of global commercial production [4]. BPA, a petroleum-derived compound, has raised significant concern within the polymer industry due to its toxicity; it is classified as a reproductive hazard in Canada, the European Union, and in numerous U.S. states. Nevertheless, it remains widely used, underscoring the need for safer, bio-based substitutes. In this context, EVOs have gained attention as promising renewable alternatives to BPA-based epoxy precursors [4].

Introducing epoxy groups into the fatty-acid chains of vegetable oils increases their reactivity and broadens their potential in polymerization and crosslinking reactions. EVOs can be directly polymerized using acid catalysts such as boron trifluoride diethyl etherate, various metal triflates, or tris(pentafluorophenyl)borane, producing thermosetting networks with adjustable mechanical and thermal characteristics (Figure 2). EVOs can also be cured with a wide variety of hardeners – including amines, anhydrides, and carboxylic acids – to create resins that span a wide range of stiffness and heat resistance [13-18]. These bio-based epoxy materials generally offer good flexibility and notable thermal durability, although their mechanical strength and chemical resistance often remain below those of traditional petroleum-derived epoxy systems.

It is also notable that epoxidized castor, soybean, and linseed oils can be effectively polymerized using UV initiators; however, this photopolymerization approach is generally better suited to coatings and thin films because ultraviolet light cannot penetrate deeply into thicker materials [19-20].

Among the various EVOs, epoxidized linseed oil (ELO) is particularly noteworthy because its high degree of unsaturation results in a high epoxy functionality after epoxidation. The elevated oxirane content makes ELO a highly reactive and sustainable building block for thermosetting polymers [14, 15, 17]. With an epoxide functionality typically exceeding five, it forms cured networks with high crosslink density. Our work has demonstrated that ELO can be efficiently crosslinked using Lewis acid catalysts and bio-derived acids to yield fully renewable resins that exhibit satisfactory mechanical properties and thermal stability. The following section provides a more detailed discussion of the rationale behind selecting ELO as the bio-based epoxy precursor.

2.1 Criteria for selecting the appropriate EVOs

Two criteria are considered when selecting bio-based epoxy resins derived from vegetable oils. The first criterion is the availability of the resin on an industrial scale, as this significantly influences the price of EVO. The second criterion is the number of epoxy groups present in the oil molecule. A higher number of epoxy groups leads to increased crosslinking in the resulting thermoset, which enhances its mechanical strength. ELO was selected because it meets both criteria optimally. For instance, while epoxidized soybean oil is produced on an industrial

scale, it contains an average of only 4.2 meq/g of epoxy groups, compared to ELO's 5.6 meq/g (further experimental evidence comparing ELO and ESO is provided in Appendix C). On the other hand, epoxidized perilla oil has a higher epoxy group content at 6.6 meq/g, but its production is very limited and primarily used for food applications [10, 21-23].

When comparing ELO to petroleum-based epoxy resins based on BPA like diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), two significant issues arise. First, the epoxy groups in DGEBA are located at the ends of the molecule (external), which grants them higher reactivity and easier access to react with epoxy groups on other molecules. In contrast, the epoxy groups in ELO are situated internally, resulting in lower reactivity and more limited access to other molecules' epoxy groups. This makes it difficult to form a densely crosslinked network in this biomaterial. Second, the presence of aromatic rings in the DGEBA structure contributes to the stiffness and mechanical strength of the resulting polymer. In contrast, ELO consists solely of long aliphatic chains, which provide flexibility and a lower glass transition temperature in the resulting thermoset. This characteristic of ELO further complicates the achievement of a thermoset with high mechanical strength [10, 24-26] (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Chemical structures of DGEBA and ELO, highlighting their key differences.

2.2 Strategies for achieving optimal thermosets from ELO

In response to the challenges mentioned, the research in the project BIOBUILD was aimed to achieve five key characteristics of the bio-binders namely, to be *bio-based*, *possessing sufficient mechanical strength*, *curing at relatively low temperatures*, *curing within a short time*, and *being economically feasible*. To meet these objectives, three strategies were examined to develop thermosets from ELO that satisfies the above-mentioned criteria. These strategies are as follows:

- Examining the performance of homopolymerization catalysts, which can ensure a high bio-content in the final thermoset binder.
- Investigating the effect of incorporating aromatic rings into the thermoset binder structure on mechanical strength, by using aromatic ring-containing hardeners.
- Evaluating the impact of increased crosslink density on the binder's mechanical strength using multifunctional hardeners with small molecules.

3. Examining the performance of homopolymerization catalysts

3.1 Sample preparation with aluminum trifluoromethanesulfonate and tris(pentafluorophenyl)borane catalysts

ELO's homopolymerization catalysts primarily belong to the Lewis acid family and are used in very small quantities (up to 1-2% wt.). These catalysts facilitate the cationic ring-opening polymerization of epoxy groups. In our study, we employed aluminum trifluoromethanesulfonate $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and tris(pentafluorophenyl)borane (BCF), both of which are strong Lewis's acids, to compare their performance. Although these substances are not biomolecules, their minimal usage (up to 1% wt., [25, 27]) does not significantly reduce the bio-content of the final thermosets. We experimented with two concentrations and curing temperatures for ELO using these catalysts.

Figure 5 illustrates the structure of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$, along with a schematic representation of the crosslinked polymer (homopolymerized) produced using this catalyst. It also displays two thermoset pieces made from ELO cured with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at two different concentrations.

Figure 5. Two thermoset pieces made from ELO and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$. The curing conditions are specified; the chemical structure of the catalyst is presented alongside a schematic representation of crosslinked ELO molecules.

Accordingly, Figure 6 presents the structure of BCF, accompanied by two thermoset pieces made from ELO and BCF at two concentrations. The concentrations and curing conditions were identical for both catalysts.

Figure 6. Two thermoset samples composed of cured ELO by BCF. The curing conditions are detailed in the figure along with the chemical structure of the catalyst.

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

To investigate ELO curing with these catalysts in greater detail, we conducted differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments. Figure 7 presents the DSC thermograms for ELO curing with $Al(OTf)_3$ and BFC at two concentrations, alongside pure ELO (without catalyst).

The first observation from the graph is that the peaks are very sharp, indicating a high reaction rate for ELO curing with this catalyst. This supports the theory that the reaction terminates rapidly due to a sudden increase in medium viscosity. The second observation relates to the effect of catalyst concentration on the onset temperature (T_{onset}) and peak temperature (T_{peak}), as shown in Table 3. As the concentration of the catalyst increases, both T_{onset} and T_{peak} decrease, suggesting that the reaction occurs at lower temperatures with higher catalyst concentrations. Additionally, the enthalpy of reaction (ΔH) increases with higher catalyst concentrations, indicating that more epoxy groups are being consumed. Notably, no peaks are observed in the DSC thermogram of pure ELO, which demonstrates that ELO does not undergo thermal homopolymerization in the absence of a catalyst, even at temperatures exceeding 250 °C.

Figure 7. DSC thermograms of the ELO curing reaction with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF at two concentrations, alongside the DSC thermogram of ELO without catalyst. The heating rate was set at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The DSC thermogram of ELO curing with BCF at two concentrations shows that the curing behaviour of this catalyst is comparable to that of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$; however, T_{onset} and T_{peak} for BCF are lower, indicating that this catalyst exhibits higher reactivity and initiates the reaction at reduced temperatures as shown in [Table 3](#). Furthermore, the enthalpies of reaction obtained with the catalyst are higher than those recorded for $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$, suggesting that a larger number of epoxy groups are consumed in the presence of BCF. The effect of concentration for the catalyst reflects the behaviour observed with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$.

Table 3. Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) for the catalysts BCF and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$, at two concentrations.

Catalyst and concentration	$\Delta H(\text{J/g})$	$T_{\text{peak}} (^\circ\text{C})$	$T_{\text{onset}} (^\circ\text{C})$	$T_g (^\circ\text{C})$
$\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ 0.31% wt.	511.23	108.38	94.18	-23.11
$\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ 0.66% wt.	532.96	97.40	82.68	-23.25
BCF 0.31% wt.	612.77	79.67	57.95	-19.83
BCF 0.66% wt.	666.23	70.00	47.22	-21.12

The measurement of the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured polymers with these catalysts was carried out on the cured samples. For this purpose, they were subjected to DSC analysis in the temperature range from minus -30 to 170°C . The results are presented in [Figure 8](#) and [Table 3](#). As can be observed in [Figure 8](#), the transition corresponding to T_g appears as a small step in the DSC curve of each sample. With the temperature increase of these samples, and up to 17°C , no peak corresponding to curing is observed, indicating that either the curing has been fully completed or there is no further reaction possible for the epoxy groups due to the solidification of the samples. In general, T_g s of the polymers prepared with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ is lower than that of the polymers prepared with BCF, but this difference is not large, indicating that, at ambient temperature, these polymers are in a rubbery state. Furthermore, although the use of more catalyst leads to an increase in the ΔH , it does not have a significant effect on T_g , and no clear trend is observed. Overall, it can be concluded that the T_g of the polymers was found within the range of approximately -20 to -23.5°C .

Figure 8. DSC thermograms of the cured ELO with BCF and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at two concentrations. The heating rate was set at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

In order to investigate the consumption of epoxy groups and the chemical structural changes of ELO after curing with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectroscopy in the range of 4000 to 450 cm^{-1} was performed. The results related to the $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF are presented in [Figure 9](#).

Figure 9. FTIR spectra of pure ELO and ELO cured with Al(OTf)₃ and BCF at two concentrations.

Since different catalysts were used and their concentrations varied, it is not possible to normalize the peaks. It can be observed in the figures that the peak corresponding to the epoxy groups at around 821 cm⁻¹ has either significantly decreased or completely disappeared due to the curing reaction, both for Al(OTf)₃ catalyst and for BCF catalyst. Another point is that the formation of linear ether bonds occurs at 1078 cm⁻¹, and it can be observed that this peak is much more intense compared to pure ELO, indicating the building of ether bonds within the cured ELOs. The peak corresponding to the ester group of triglycidyl at 1740 cm⁻¹ has not undergone significant change compared to ELO, and this is expected since it is anticipated that the structure of the triglycidyl remains unchanged after curing. The peaks corresponding to the C-H stretching of aliphatic chains at 2854 cm⁻¹ (symmetric) and 2925 cm⁻¹ (asymmetric) also remain unchanged compared to the cured ELO, since the fatty acid aliphatic chains do not undergo any alterations during the curing process. Finally, The peak at 3450, corresponding to the hydroxyl group, can result from the formation of hydroxyl groups on the polymer chain in the presence of atmospheric humidity or a small amount of ethanol present in the catalysts mixture.

3.3 Selection of an appropriate catalyst concentration

The concentration range of 0.1 to 0.8% was selected for these catalysts because concentrations below 0.1% resulted in a low reaction rate. Conversely, concentrations above 0.8% not only reduced the pot life of the mixture but also led to a rapid reaction rate that generated significant heat. This excessive heat caused the polymer to foam due to thermal degradation, as illustrated in two examples shown in Figure 10.

The effects of catalyst concentration, solvent volume, heat transfer surface area, vacuum application, and other factors on the quality of the final product have been examined and documented in Appendix A.

Figure 10. Foaming of ELO during the curing reaction at high concentrations of the catalysts BCF and Al(OTf)₃.

3.4 Mechanical properties of thermosets

For the mechanical strength testing of the thermosets with Al(OTf)₃ and BCF catalysts, a tensile testing device was used. Standard aluminium mold for testing the tensile strength according to the standard [28] was prepared, and a mold release spray (8329-350G Epoxy Mold Release by MG Chemicals) was used to facilitate easy removal of the specimens from the mold. This creates a very thin, non-stick layer on the aluminium mold, which is resistant up to 200°C and ensures easy specimen release. The set prevents surface defects on the finished specimens. The mold design and dimensions of the specimens are shown in [Figure 11](#).

Figure 11. Aluminium mold (a) and dimensions of the specimen for mechanical tensile testing (b).

The tensile test was conducted at a loading rate of 5 mm/min on the specimens. In [Figure 12](#), the tensile testing set and samples after the tensile test are shown. The results of the tensile strength and elongation at failure are reported in [Table 4](#). It was observed that the performance of the BCF catalyst in terms of tensile strength is better than that of the Al(OTf)₃ catalyst. However, no clear trend was revealed regarding the concentration. For instance, in the case of Al(OTf)₃, there is no significant change in tensile strength, while for the BCF specimens, increasing the concentration leads to a decrease in tensile strength.

Figure 12. Tensile testing setup (a) and post-test specimens (b). From left to right in b): specimen cured with BCF at 0.66% wt., BCF at 0.31% wt., Al(OTf)₃ at 0.66% wt. and Al(OTf)₃ at 0.31% wt. concentrations.

Table 4. Tensile strength and elongation at break of the samples cured with the catalysts BCF and Al(OTf)₃ at two concentrations.

Catalyst and concentration, % wt	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at failure (%)
Al(OTf) ₃ 0.31	0.39 ± 0.04	8.5 ± 1.1
Al(OTf) ₃ 0.66	0.39 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 1.1
BCF 0.31	0.72 ± 0.07	6.8 ± 0.7
BCF 0.66	0.42 ± 0.02	5.0 ± 0.7

While the curing conditions for the both catalysts (60-100°C for 1-2 h) were acceptable from a technological point of view, the epoxidized oil polymers exhibited low mechanical strength attributed to a rapid increase of the substrate viscosity when 30 to 50% of the epoxy groups reacted. The increased viscosity restricted the movement of large ELO chains, and limiting the accessibility of the epoxy groups to react, thus limiting the mechanical strength of the polymer [29]. Under these conditions, reactions occurred primarily between intermolecular groups (epoxy groups of the ELO molecule). As a result, despite the reactions of the epoxy groups, effective crosslinking was not achieved.

3.5 Processing of wood composites with Al(OTf)₃ catalyst

In the next step, an attempt was made to prepare a composite containing wood particles impregnated with ethyl palmitate, ELO, and the catalyst Al(OTf)₃. A composition consisting of 50% wt. impregnated wood particles with ethyl palmitate, 37% wt. ELO, 13% wt. untreated wood fibres and (0.31 and 0.66% wt.) Al(OTf)₃ was used. The amount of the compounds in the composite was chosen based on a study [36] where similar composition was used to demonstrate the application of BCF as catalyst for ELO polymerization as a binder in the composite. The intent in the present study was to use Al(OTf)₃ as catalyst, which is available at lower cost than that of BCF.

The composites were prepared using 0.31 and 0.66% wt. Al(OTf)₃. In both cases, the composites lacked integrity as the ELO binder and Al(OTf)₃ catalyst were unable to hold the impregnated wood particles and fibres together to form an integrated composite. Processing a composite with impregnated wood particles is more difficult than a composite consisting of untreated particles – due to the reduced adhesion to the binder by the presence of ethyl palmitate on the fibre surfaces and additionally to interference of ELO polymerization – it was decided to repeat the process using only untreated wood particles. However, the results were negative. At a concentration of 0.31% wt. no bonding occurred between the particles and the binder, while at 0.66% wt. agglomerates of binder and particles were formed, but a cohesive composite structure was still not achieved (Figure 13). Thus, the attempts to produce a composite using the Al(OTf)₃ catalyst were unsuccessful and the catalyst discarded for further tests.

Figure 13. Agglomerates of binder and wood particles with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst at 0.66% wt. (a) and an integrated composite using BCF catalyst (b).

Based on the results, the next essential step was to study and explore methods to enhance the mechanical strength of the binder. One factor that can potentially increase the mechanical strength and stiffness of polymers is the presence of aromatic rings in their structure. Therefore, in the subsequent phase – referred to as the second strategy – consisting of incorporation of aromatic rings into the thermoset by using hardeners that contain aromatic rings. This approach aims to investigate the impact of the aromatic rings on the mechanical strength of the thermosets.

4. Incorporating aromatic rings into the thermoset binder structure

4.1 Diphenylamine

The presence of aromatic rings in the thermoset structure can potentially enhance its mechanical strength by restricting chain mobility and increasing stiffness [12, 30]. In order to study this effect, diphenylamine, which contains two aromatic rings, was used as a hardener. Although it is not bio-based and recommended to be added in quantities we selected to investigate the impact of the aromatic ring on mechanical strength at 20% wt. of the catalyst. In contrast to catalysts, hardeners must be used in stoichiometric amounts to achieve the desired properties of the final thermosets. This means that one molecule of a catalyst increases the chemical reaction speed for a large number of epoxy groups, whereas an active group of a hardener molecule can only react with a single epoxy group.

For example, in the case of diphenylamine, there is only one active hydrogen atom available (the one attached to the nitrogen atom), and therefore, to consume each epoxy group by diphenylamine, one diphenylamine molecule is needed. This explains the significant amount of hardener needed in the reaction.

If a molecule of ELO contains six epoxy groups, six molecules of diphenylamine are required for reaction of all epoxy groups. The molecular weight of ELO is approximately 1000 g/mol and that of diphenylamine is 169 g/mol, the stoichiometric ratio of ELO to diphenylamine is ca. 50:50 by weight. However, such a formulation would significantly reduce the bio-content of the final product, since diphenylamine is not a bio-based compound. Therefore, a test with 10% wt. diphenylamine was carried out.

The sample prepared from ELO and diphenylamine was initially kept at 60°C for 2 h; however, no reaction occurred during this period, and the mixture remained in the liquid phase. Consequently, the temperature increased to 100°C, and the sample was kept for 20 h. No reaction was observed after 20 h and the temperature was raised to 180°C to keep the sample for another 20 h. No reaction occurred between diphenylamine and ELO, and it was concluded that 10% wt. diphenylamine was insufficient to initiate curing of ELO.

In the next step, 20% wt. diphenylamine was used, and the above procedure was repeated. The sample was first kept at 60°C for 2 h to observe a lack of reaction and the mixture remained in liquid phase. The temperature increased to 100°C and maintained for 20 h with no signs of reaction. Subsequently, the reaction temperature

was raised to 180°C, and the sample was kept for another 20 h to observe that the ELO was polymerized to a flexible polymer after the above conditions.

The low polymer yield can be attributed to several factors, namely use of less than the stoichiometric amount of hardener and low reactivity of diphenylamine at test temperatures. Although diphenylamine contains two aromatic rings that could potentially increase the stiffness of the final polymer, as a secondary amine it can react only on one side and therefore cannot contribute to cross-linking within the polymer network. Consequently, while the presence of aromatic groups might enhance stiffness, the lack of sufficient network formation ultimately leads to reduced rigidity in the final material.

The use of diphenylamine as a hardener was considered unsuccessful. The curing temperature and time required were high (above 180°C and 20 h), and the final product obtained was a flexible polymer.

The chemical structure of diphenylamine is shown in Figure 14. The Figure presents an ELO mixture containing 20% wt. of diphenylamine, which remained a viscous liquid after 20 h at 100°C. When the temperature increased to 180°C, a solid but yet flexible polymer was obtained after 20 h.

Figure 14. Chemical structure of diphenylamine, a sample of ELO and diphenylamine after 20 h at 100°C, and another sample cured for 20 h at 180°C.

4.2 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid

3,4-diaminobenzoic acid containing both amine and carboxylic acid functional groups, and an aromatic ring was tested as hardener. Like diphenylamine, 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid acts as a hardener and must be used in stoichiometric amounts to achieve the desired properties in the thermoset.

3,4-diaminobenzoic acid molecule possesses five reactive sites – four amine hydrogens and one carboxylic acid group – approximately 6/5 of a 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid molecule is required to fully react with one ELO molecule. The molar mass of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid is 152 g/mol and thus, 182.4 g of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid is needed per 1000 g of ELO. Therefore, the stoichiometric weight ratio of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid to ELO is 18% wt.

The polymerization test started at a concentration of 10% wt. to minimize the reduction in bio-content of the final thermoset. A mixture containing 10% wt. of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid was prepared and maintained at 60°C for 2 h. No reaction occurred during this stage; the mixture remained in liquid form. It should be noted that due to the low solubility of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid in organic solvents, the compound was added to ELO either as a solid powder or as a dispersion in the solvent.

In the next step, the temperature increased to 100°C for 20 h; however, no reaction occurred, only a color change was observed in the solution. The reaction mixture was heated to 180°C and kept at this temperature for 20 h. The viscosity of the liquid increased significantly resulting in a paste-like material, but solid polymer was not obtained.

The experiment was repeated at 18% wt. 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid and identical conditions. By heating at 100°C for 20 h, the mixture became highly viscous but did not solidify yet. When the temperature was increased to 130°C for 20 h, a hard polymer with high mechanical strength was obtained.

The chemical structure of this multifunctional aromatic hardener is illustrated in Figure 15. This hardener can participate in an epoxy ring-opening reaction via both its acid and amine groups. Curing temperature of 100°C

is low for this hardener, as the mixture remains liquid-like even after 20 h and after the increase of the temperature to 130°C, the thermoset exhibited a solid state.

Figure 15. Chemical structure of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid, a sample of ELO and 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid after 20 h at 100°C, and another sample cured for 20 h at 130°C.

Regarding the experiments conducted with 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid, several conclusions can be drawn. Replacing the secondary amine with a primary amine and a carboxylic acid group significantly increased the reactivity of the hardener. As a result, instead of reacting at 180°C to produce a flexible polymer (in case of diphenylamine), the reaction occurred at 130°C, yielding a hard polymer. However, it should be noted that the reaction time remains impractical for composite applications, since maintaining the composite at 130°C for 20 h may intensify the leaching of ethyl palmitate from the wood particles and is also highly energy demanding.

Furthermore, as mentioned earlier, 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid is a non-bio-based compound, and using 18% wt. of it in the thermoset formulation reduces significantly the bio-content of the final product. Although the experiment did not achieve the desired practical outcomes, it clearly demonstrated that the presence of an aromatic ring, combined with the ability to form a three-dimensional network using a multifunctional hardener, can substantially enhance the mechanical strength of the resulting polymer.

On the other hand, the results obtained from the first strategy showed that the homopolymerization of ELO, regardless of the catalyst type, does not lead to polymers with high mechanical strength. As the reaction proceeds and the viscosity increases, the large ELO molecules are unable to move and interact freely, which prevents the formation of a densely crosslinked network.

In contrast, the results from the second strategy demonstrated that using a sufficiently small hardener containing two or more functional groups and an aromatic ring can result in the formation of a polymer with significantly improved mechanical strength. The aromatic ring itself, as previously shown, contributes to enhanced mechanical performance. Meanwhile, the presence of two or more functional groups promotes crosslink formation and the development of a three-dimensional network. Additionally, the small molecular size of the hardener facilitates diffusion even at high viscosities, thereby ensuring effective crosslinking under such conditions.

Based on the findings, it should be noted that bio-based molecules containing aromatic rings are often relatively large, e.g., lignin. These large molecules encounter difficulties diffusing and moving within highly viscous systems. Therefore, in the next step, rather than focusing on incorporating an aromatic ring into the thermoset structure, attention was directed toward employing smaller hardener molecules with at least two functional groups. This approach aimed to ensure sufficient diffusivity even at elevated viscosities and to increase the crosslink density in the final polymer through the presence of multiple reactive groups. This concept formed the foundation of the third strategy, which was subsequently investigated in the study.

5. Application of small multifunctional hardeners

5.1 Maleic anhydride

Maleic anhydride, which contains two functional carbonyl groups, was used to investigate the effect of hardener size and functionality. Maleic anhydride can react by both carbonyl groups with two epoxy groups of epoxidized oil and thereby serves as a crosslinked polymer. Its molecular weight of 98 g/mol allows an easy diffusion in highly viscous systems. Furthermore, maleic anhydride exhibits high solubility in organic solvents, including acetone, and its melting point is below 60°C, allowing it to be used in either solution form or as a solid hardener for ELO.

Since maleic anhydride has two reactive groups, three molecules are required per ELO molecule to react with all six epoxy groups. Considering the molecular weights of ELO and maleic anhydride, the stoichiometric amount corresponds to 27% wt.%. Although some bio-based production methods have been proposed [31, 32], the majority of maleic anhydride is still derived from petroleum sources. Consequently, using the full stoichiometric amount would significantly reduce the bio-content of the final product. Therefore, the test included a gradual increase of maleic anhydride, i.e., 5, 10, 17 and 33% wt. and curing temperature of 110°C for 1.5 h.

The sample containing 5% wt. maleic anhydride resulted in a flexible polymer. Visual (subjective) evaluations of its mechanical strength indicated that it was only slightly better than the sample prepared using the $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst. However, the curing temperature and time were relatively favorable. Subjective evaluations of the sample with 10% wt. maleic anhydride showed no significant difference in mechanical properties to the sample with 5% wt. With an increase of maleic anhydride concentration (17 and 33% wt.), the curing temperature of the samples decreased. Apart from the changes in the curing reaction temperature and sample colors, no significant differences were observed among the samples. For instance, their mechanical properties showed minimal variation; the samples became slightly more rigid. Overall, the mechanical properties of these samples were similar to those of the polymers obtained using the $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst.

Figure 17 shows solid thermosets with maleic anhydride and reaction conditions. The chemical structure of maleic anhydride is also depicted in this figure, highlighting its small molecular mass and bulk molecular volume. Additionally, the figure includes a schematic illustrating how ELO is crosslinked with this hardener.

When a sample containing 10% wt. maleic anhydride was cured at 160°C for 1.5 h, the solidification occurred faster due to the higher reaction rate. However, no other noticeable differences were observed in the sample compared to the one cured at 110°C, Figure 16. It can be concluded that the temperature and maleic anhydride concentration primarily influenced the rate of solidification and the curing temperature but had little or no effect on the mechanical properties of the samples. Further investigations on maleic anhydride as a hardener, including the effects of solvent-free addition and the combined use of maleic anhydride with a catalyst, are presented in detail in Appendix B.

Given the favorable curing temperature and time achieved with maleic anhydride, it was decided that the third strategy would proceed along two possible paths, aiming not only to maintain optimal curing conditions but also to maximize mechanical properties. Accordingly, the next steps focused on using either a molecule with a higher number of functional groups (path 1) or use of small molecules (path 2). Citric acid was therefore selected as the next hardener to be tested.

Figure 16. Chemical structure of maleic anhydride, thermosets using this hardener and a schematic representation of ELO molecules crosslinked by maleic anhydride.

5.2 Citric acid

Molecules of citric acid are small and have four functional groups, three carboxylic acid groups and one hydroxyl group; citric acid is derived from natural sources [12]. Citric acid can react with epoxy groups through its carboxylic acid functionalities, opening the epoxy rings and forming ester bonds. The hydroxyl group in citric acid can also participate in ring-opening reactions with epoxy groups; however, its reactivity is lower than that of the acidic groups [33]. Therefore, citric acid potentially reacts with at least three epoxy groups, and the resulting three-dimensional network is expected to be denser than that formed by maleic anhydride as the hardener.

Considering the molecular weight of citric acid (192 g/mol, monohydrate type molecular weight is 210 g/mol) and assuming four reactive groups for it, approximately 1.5 moles of citric acid are required to react with the epoxy groups in one ELO molecule. Therefore, the stoichiometric ratio between the reactive groups of citric acid and ELO corresponds to 28% wt. Citric acid is a fully bio-based molecule and its cost is comparable to that of ELO, i.e., use of relatively high amounts of it is justified.

Citric acid of 13% wt. was dissolved in acetone and added to ELO. The obtained mixture was kept at 60°C for 3 h to allow solvent evaporation, followed by curing at 120°C for 1 h to produce a solid polymer. To ensure complete curing, the sample was further heated at 180°C for 1 h. The thermoset produced from this sample was significantly stiffer and tougher compared to the previously obtained samples. A drawback was the

appearance of cracks, probably caused by shrinkage during curing (Figure 17b). Due to the adhesion of these thermosets, they could not be easily removed from the curing container.

Unlike maleic anhydride, citric acid has a melting point above 150°C, making its use in molten form with ELO impractical. Therefore, a dispersion of citric acid particles mixed with ELO and subjected to curing was tested. A sample of 20% wt. solid citric acid particles was cured at 120°C for 1 h followed by a post-curing step at 180°C for another hour. The resulting polymer exhibited desirable mechanical properties and showed fewer cracks compared to the previous sample. However, due to the presence of relatively large citric acid particles, the obtained material resembled more of a composite rather than a homogenous thermoset (Figure 17a).

Figure 17. Chemical structure of citric acid, thermosets using this hardener and a schematic representation of ELO molecules crosslinked by citric acid.

To reduce the particle size of citric acid and improve its dispersion in ELO, citric acid powder was ground to obtain fine powder. Using these finer particles, a new sample containing 20% wt. citric acid was prepared and cured at 120°C for 1 h (Figure 17c). As a result of the reduced particle size, the uniformity of the prepared sample improved, leading to a more homogeneous thermoset compared to the previous one.

To further a more uniform distribution in ELO, 20% wt. citric acid was first dissolved in acetone, and the resulting solution was added to ELO. The mixture was stirred for 15 min to obtain a completely homogeneous solution at molecular level. Prior to curing, the sample was subjected to vacuum for 15 min to remove the solvent, preventing the formation of cracks as observed in the first sample. The sample was then cured at 120°C for 1.5 h. As shown in Figure 17d, the thermoset obtained was homogeneous and exhibited good mechanical properties as those of the previous samples. Citric acid meets all required criteria, by being fully bio-based, having a short curing time, reasonable cost, and providing desirable mechanical properties. However, a reduction in the curing temperature makes citric acid an appropriate candidate for further upscaling.

Citric acid of 20% wt. and 0.31% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst were mixed and cured with ELO at reduced temperature from 120°C to 80°C and time from 1.5 to 1 h. However, the mechanical properties of the polymer decreased significantly (Figure 17e).

It was observed that when the mixture reached 80°C, $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst initiated the solidification reaction, which occurred before the temperature was sufficiently high to initiate the reaction with citric acid, i.e., citric acid did not react in the system. Therefore, it can be concluded that the combination of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst and citric acid is ineffective, as each component acts independently rather than synergistically.

Based on the successful performance of imidazole in enhancing the reactivity of maleic anhydride (see Appendix B for experimental evidence, as well as [14, 15]), a sample of 20% wt. citric acid and 2% wt. of imidazole as a catalyst was prepared. However, unlikely the results with maleic anhydride, imidazole did not react effectively in combination with citric acid. The solidification and curing of the polymer occurred only when the temperature reached 120°C, and no reduction in the curing temperature was observed (Figure 18). At this point, efforts to lower the curing temperature of citric acid and ELO were discontinued. It is concluded that citric acid is an effective hardener for ELO, which justified further study of its properties.

Figure 18. Sample cured with 20% wt. citric acid and 2% wt. imidazole at 120°C for 1.5 h.

5.2.1 Differential scanning calorimetry and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy

Curing reaction of ELO with citric acid was studied by DSC over a temperature range from 25 to 250°C. The resulting thermogram is shown in Figure 19a.

As seen in the Figure, an endothermic peak appears around 60°C. Since citric acid monohydrate was used in this experiment, the peak is attributed to loss of water. After the endothermic peak corresponding to water evaporation, the curing reaction begins, producing a relatively broad exothermic peak compared to those observed with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts.

The following broad peak indicates that the curing reaction of ELO with citric acid, unlike the reactions catalyzed by the aforementioned catalysts, is time-consuming. This slower reaction rate may prevent a sudden increase in viscosity, premature solidification, and the subsequent interruption of the reaction.

Another observation in the thermogram is the occurrence of a melting peak of citric acid at 153°C. This melting peak overlaps with the curing peak, and after the completion of the endothermic melting process of citric acid, the exothermic curing reaction of ELO continues. The data related to the T_{onset} , T_{peak} , and ΔH of the curing reaction are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) under curing of ELO with citric acid.

Catalyst and concentration	$\Delta H(\text{J/g})$	$T_{\text{peak}} (\text{°C})$	$T_{\text{onset}} (\text{°C})$	$T_g (\text{°C})$
Citric acid 28% wt.	256.62	125.3	72.8	5.56

Figure 19. DSC thermogram (a) of ELO curing reaction with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio and deconvolution of overlapping melting and curing peaks (b) of ELO-citric acid system. Heating rate of 5°C/min.

Since the melting peak of citric acid and the curing peak of ELO overlapped, it was necessary to separate them to calculate the enthalpy of ELO-citric acid curing reaction. A two-peak Gaussian model was used to deconvolute the two overlapping peaks. Both peaks were fitted simultaneously using non-linear least-squares optimization, and the baseline was corrected to zero. The result of deconvolution process is shown in [Figure 19b](#) where the exothermic curing peak of the ELO-citric acid reaction and the endothermic melting peak of citric acid are both displayed. By calculating the area under the curing peak, the ΔH of the curing reaction was determined ([Table 5](#)).

The cured sample was subjected to DSC analysis over a temperature range from -20 to 170°C to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the resulting polymer. The thermogram is shown in [Figure 20](#). As observed in the figure, the transition corresponding to the glass transition temperature appears as a relatively small step at 5.5°C. The thermogram demonstrated also the presence of an additional transition at 79°C. This minor peak may correspond to the reaction of residual citric acid remaining in the system. However, since the melting peak of citric acid (153°C) is no longer observed, it can be concluded that no unreacted citric acid remained in the system after this heating cycle.

By comparing the glass transition temperature of the polymer obtained using citric acid as hardener with those obtained by $Al(OTf)_3$ and BCF catalysts, it is evident that the T_g of the citric acid-cured polymer is ca. 25-30°C higher. This indicates that the resulting polymer possesses higher stiffness.

Figure 20. DSC thermogram of cured ELO with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of 5°C/min.

FTIR tests were performed to investigate the curing reaction of ELO with citric acid. The results are shown in Figure 21 where the FTIR spectra of citric acid, the mixture of citric acid and ELO (with a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups) before curing, and ELO cured with citric acid at 120°C for 1.5 h are presented. The measurements were conducted in the range of 4000 to 450 cm^{-1} . The test conditions were identical to those used for the samples containing $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts.

Figure 21. FTIR spectrums of pure citric acid, ELO and citric acid mixture before curing and cured ELO with citric acid.

In the FTIR spectrum of pure citric acid, a broad peak is observed around 3300 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the stretching vibration of hydroxyl (OH) groups present in the citric acid structure. The peaks in the range of 1685–1727 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of carbonyl (C=O) groups in the carboxylic acid groups of citric acid. The peaks at 1107 and 1209 cm^{-1} are assigned to the stretching of non-acidic hydroxyl groups (i.e., hydroxyls not attached to carboxylic acid groups). The peak around 779 cm^{-1} is attributed to the rocking vibration of methylene (CH_2) groups.

In the FTIR spectrum of the ELO-citric acid mixture before curing, two main peaks are observed: one corresponding to hydroxyl groups of citric acid at 3477 cm^{-1} and another one at 821 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the epoxy groups of ELO. The ester carbonyl peak of triglycerides appears around 1740 cm^{-1} , while the C–H stretching bands of aliphatic chains are located at 2854 and 2925 cm^{-1} , as previously discussed.

Regarding the spectrum of the cured thermoset (ELO-citric acid mixture after curing), the hydroxyl peak around 3477 cm^{-1} becomes more intense, indicating that epoxy ring-opening reactions have occurred, forming ester bonds and new hydroxyl groups. Therefore, the increase in hydroxyl peak intensity reflects the progress of the curing reaction. Some studies have also suggested the possibility of esterification reactions between the newly formed hydroxyl groups and citric acid [34]; however, such reactions are unlikely to occur at 120°C.

Another observation is the absence of the epoxy peak at 821 cm^{-1} confirming that the epoxy groups have been consumed during the curing process. Finally, a small shoulder appears on the ester carbonyl peak at 1711 cm^{-1} . This minor shoulder suggests the presence of a small amount of unreacted carboxylic acid in the system, which is consistent with the DSC results. It is worth mentioning that due to the strong ester carbonyl peak at 1740 cm^{-1} , which is associated with the triglyceride ester bonds in the ELO structure, it is difficult to track the increase in ester bond formation using FTIR. Therefore, monitoring the decrease in epoxy peak intensity together with the increase in hydroxyl peak intensity provides a more reliable approach to follow the curing reaction.

5.2.2 Mechanical properties and thermal resistance of thermosets with citric acid

Tensile tests were performed to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the resulting thermoset. The testing conditions, equipment used, strain rate, and sample dimensions were identical to those used for the thermosets

prepared with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts. Figure 22 shows samples of ELO-citric acid after the tensile test. The measured tensile strength was 4.11 MPa and 23% elongation at failure.

The tensile strength obtained was significantly higher than that of the samples prepared by $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts (Table 4). Moreover, the elongation at break for this sample was also significantly higher than that of the $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ - and BCF-catalyzed samples, indicating that this material exhibits not only high tensile strength but also high toughness.

Figure 22. Post-test specimens of ELO cured with citric acid (with a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups) at 120°C for 1.5 h (left) and TGA graph of cured ELO with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio (right). Heating rate of 10°C/min.

The mechanical testing results clearly demonstrate that the thermoset cured with citric acid possesses better mechanical properties compared to those cured with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$, BCF, maleic anhydride, and other catalysts or hardeners. The findings indicate that the third strategy, involving the use of small, multifunctional hardener molecules, is an effective approach compared to the other two strategies. This method not only provides fully bio-based thermosets but also yields desirable mechanical performance. Although the curing temperature remains above 100°C, the required curing time is short. It is also worth noting that, from an economic standpoint, citric acid has lower cost than ELO.

The thermal stability of the thermoset obtained from curing ELO with citric acid was evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The TGA test was carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°C/min. The results are presented in Figure 22 depicting the temperature corresponding to 5% weight loss (T_5), the temperature at the maximum degradation rate (T_{max}), and the residual weight at 600°C.

According to the results, T_5 is 140°C, which is attributed to the loss of moisture and any volatile compounds in the thermoset. Another noticeable weight loss occurs at 206°C, likely due to the thermal decomposition of residual unreacted citric acid in the system. The maximum decomposition rate is observed at 410°C, which corresponds to the breakdown of ester bonds and decomposition of the thermoset structure. Upon further heating to 600°C, less than 0.5% residue remains, indicating almost complete thermal degradation of the material. Apart from the initial weight loss due to moisture evaporation and the thermal decomposition of residual citric acid in the system, it can be concluded that the thermoset obtained from citric acid exhibits good thermal stability. The decomposition of ester bonds begins at a relatively high temperature of 300°C, with the maximum degradation occurring at 410°C, which is sufficient for a thermoset intended for wood-composite applications. A factor contributing to the high thermal stability of the resulting thermoset could be the presence of long aliphatic chains derived from the fatty acids in ELO, as aliphatic chains generally provide good thermal resistance.

5.2.3 Processing of wood composites with citric acid as hardener

In order to verify the results of citric acid hardening performance, wood-based composites using the bio-based binder (ELO + citric acid) were processed. Samples of particleboards (9 × 90 × 90 mm) were prepared with 33% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 17% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers and 50% wt. binder composed of 37.5% ELO and 12.5% citric acid. The citric acid content in the binder was set to 25% wt. of the ELO amount. The reason for using slightly less than the stoichiometric amount of citric acid was based on previous laboratory results (from FTIR, DSC, and TGA analyses), which indicated that when a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups was used, part of the citric acid remained unreacted.

Wood particles and fibers were mixed, citric acid was dissolved in ethanol and added to ELO. The mixture was stirred at room temperature until it became homogeneous. The binder mixture was added to the wood particle–fiber blend and mixed thoroughly. The resulting mixture was placed into a Teflon mold (as shown in Figure 27). To prevent the cured composite from sticking to the upper aluminum part of the mold, non-stick baking paper was used. The mold was pressed at 1.2-1.5 MPa pressure to produce a composite with the above dimensions. After 10 min, the pressure was released, and the mold secured with hand clamps was transferred into an oven at 120°C for curing for 1 h.

The composites are illustrated in Figure 23. Although the composite performed significantly better than the one prepared by $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst, it still lacked sufficient mechanical strength. Despite prolonged mixing, the binder distribution throughout the composite was not completely uniform, the solidification of the binder limited the ability of ELO to fully penetrate all regions of the composite during the curing,

Figure 23. Composite containing 33% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 17% wt. CTMP birch fibers and 50% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid) prepared in solution form.

Identical wood composition was tested with a difference that citric acid was dissolved in ethanol, the solution added to the wood sawdust and fibers and mixed and ELO was added to the mixture. The pressing and curing conditions were kept identical to those of the previous test. This method was intended to achieve a more uniform distribution of the hardener within the composite. Since ELO itself does not contain hardener, it can penetrate better under pressure and elevated temperature (pressing and curing) before solidification. As the hardener (citric acid) is already distributed throughout the composite, curing occurs locally wherever ELO encounters it. The composites are shown in Figure 24. The resulting material exhibited desirable mechanical strength and formed a uniform and cohesive structure. Therefore, keeping the citric acid and ELO separated prior to curing is a practically effective strategy for wood-based composites.

Figure 24. Composites containing 33% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 17% wt. CTMP birch fibers and 50% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid). Citric acid solution was added to the wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.

Considering the effective method of adding citric acid solution to wood fibers instead of mixing with ELO, the next step was to reduce the binder content from 50 to 30% wt. %. Accordingly, a composite was prepared consisting of 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 30.2% wt. binder composed of ELO and citric acid. Identically, to the previous composites, citric acid content in the binder was set at 25% wt. and thus, the composition was 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid.

However, the obtained composite lacked sufficient mechanical strength and structural integrity due to increase of the wood fractions and decrease of binder amount. As shown in [Figure 25](#), the composite could not retain its shape. It is important to note that lower binder content is desirable in particleboard production, since the cost of wood fibers and particles is lower than that of the binder. Therefore, it is advantageous to minimize the binder percentage while maintaining adequate mechanical strength.

Figure 25. Composite containing 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid. Citric acid solution was added to the wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.

Although dissolving citric acid in ethanol and adding it to the wood fibers produced satisfactory results when using 50% wt. binder, reducing the total binder content (i.e., the combined amount of ELO and citric acid) did not yield favorable outcomes. One possible explanation for the unsatisfactory results is that dissolving citric acid and adding it to the fibers in solution form leads to penetration of citric acid into the porous particle/fiber structure, making it less accessible to ELO.

Another test used citric acid added in finely powdered form directly to the mixture of wood particles and fibers. Composition identical to the previous test namely, 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid was studied. This approach was expected to increase the accessibility of citric acid for reaction with ELO while maintaining a uniform distribution throughout the mixture.

The wood particles and fibers were mixed, powdered citric acid was added, and mixing was continued. Finally, ELO was added to the mixture. The resulting blend was then molded using the same mold and cured under identical conditions as in the previous composites.

The composite obtained by this method (Figure 26) exhibited an integrated structure and desirable mechanical properties. Overall, this experiment, together with the previous ones, clarified two key points regarding the preparation process of composites using citric acid:

- To enhance the penetration of ELO throughout the composite, the hardener (citric acid) must be used separately from ELO, rather than being directly mixed with it.
- Citric acid must remain as accessible as possible to ELO during curing. Dissolving and adding it to wood fibers or particles may cause reduction of its availability for reaction with ELO.

Therefore, using finely powdered solid citric acid effectively satisfies both requirements, ensuring uniform distribution of the hardener while maintaining its accessibility for reaction with ELO.

Figure 26. Composite containing 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid. Citric acid fine powder was added to wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.

Composites with impregnated sawdust particles with ethyl palmitate

A composite containing 45% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust, 15% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 40% wt. binder consisting of ELO and powdered citric acid (75:25). In the first step, the impregnated pine particles were mixed with wood fibers by mechanical mixing with intermittent resting periods for a total of one hour. After that, powdered citric acid was added to the mixture and stirred for 5 min, followed by the addition of ELO, and mixing for another 5 min. The molding and curing conditions were the same as those used for the previous composites. As shown in Figure 27, the composite produced using this composition and method exhibited good structural integrity and satisfactory mechanical properties. Therefore, it was confirmed that the binder formulation and preparation method developed are also applicable to impregnated wood particles, yielding desirable and consistent results.

Figure 27. Composite containing 45% wt. impregnated Scots pine particles, 15% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 40% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid, 75:25).

Considering that increased amount of impregnated particles in the final product not only offers economic advantages but also contributes to enhanced thermal storage capacity, the proportion of impregnated pine particles was tested at 50 and 60% wt. Accordingly, the former option contained 50% wt. impregnated Scots pine particles, 10% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 40% wt. % binder, (ELO-citric acid 75:25). The latter option had a composition of 60% wt. impregnated Scots pine particles, 14% wt. CTMP birch fibers and 26% wt. binder (ELO-citric acid 72:28). Both options resulted in composites with good structural integrity and satisfactory mechanical strength, confirming the suitability of this formulation even with the higher proportion of impregnated pine particles ([Figure 28](#)).

Figure 28. Composite containing 50% (a) and 60% (b) impregnated Scots pine particles.

5.3 Oxalic acid

Oxalic acid is another bio-based hardener containing two carboxylic acid groups. Oxalic acid is the smallest dicarboxylic acid, with a molar mass of 90 g/mol. When the ratio of the number of functional groups to molar mass is used as criterion, oxalic acid yields a higher value than citric acid (Equations 1 and 2). This means that the number of functional groups per unit molar mass is greater for oxalic acid. Therefore, oxalic acid is expected to perform similarly or better than citric acid.

Equation 1: Functional groups per unit molar mass for citric acid (considering or ignoring hydroxyl groups, for anhydrous and monohydrate forms): $3/210 - 4/192 = 0.0142 - 0.0208$

Equation 2: Functional groups per unit of molar mass for oxalic acid: $2/90 = 0.0222$

In addition, the acid strength of oxalic acid is characterized by $pK_{a1} \approx 1.25$ and $pK_{a2} \approx 4.27$ [35]. In comparison, citric acid has $pK_{a1} \approx 3.13$, $pK_{a2} \approx 4.76$, and $pK_{a3} \approx 6.4$ [35]. The comparison indicates that oxalic acid is stronger than citric acid. Therefore, from the perspective of acidity, oxalic acid is also expected to exhibit higher reactivity.

Considering the molar mass of oxalic acid and the fact that it contains two acidic groups, three molecules of oxalic acid are required to react with all six epoxy groups on ELO. Therefore, the stoichiometric ratio between epoxy groups and carboxylic groups when using oxalic acid corresponds to 27% wt. and is similar to that of citric acid.

Based on previous experience with curing ELO with citric acid, the steps previously performed – such as evaluating the effect of adding a solvent, solvent removal under vacuum, and particle size of acid powder – were not repeated for curing ELO with oxalic acid. Instead, fine oxalic acid powder was directly used in the stoichiometric ratio for ELO curing. The resulting mixture was cured at 60°C for 1.5 h. The obtained polymer is shown in [Figure 29](#). Subjective and qualitative evaluations indicated that the mechanical strength of the polymer is adequate and comparable to that obtained with citric acid, with the only difference that the curing temperature was reduced from 120 to 60°C.

Figure 29. Samples cured with 27% wt. oxalic acid in powder form at 60°C for 1.5 h.

5.3.1 Differential scanning calorimetry and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy

A DSC analysis was first carried out under identical conditions to those used for citric acid curing, starting from 25°C and increased to 250°C, with a heating rate of 5°C/min. The thermogram of the test is shown in [Figure 30 \(left\)](#). As observed in the thermogram, T_{peak} of the ELO curing with oxalic acid occurs at 75°C, which is significantly lower than the T_{peak} for citric acid curing (i.e., 125.3°C, Table 5). However, accurate determination of the peak temperature was somewhat complicated by the simultaneous presence of an endothermic peak associated with water evaporation. It should be noted that oxalic acid, due to its strong hygroscopic nature, rapidly absorbs moisture from the air. The evaporation peak was observed at 100°C and corresponds to evaporation of absorbed moisture, not to loss of crystallization water as in the case of citric acid.

Similar to citric acid case, the curing peak of ELO with oxalic acid is broad, indicating that the curing process does not occur instantaneously as with $Al(OTf)_3$ or BCF catalysts, and the reaction does not stop prematurely due to rapid solidification. Moreover, the absence of a melting peak for oxalic acid in the DSC curve suggests

that unlikely citric acid, the total volume of oxalic acid in the mixture reacts before reaching its melting point (approximately 190°C).

Figure 30. DSC thermogram (left) of ELO curing reaction with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio and deconvolution of overlapping melting and curing peaks (right) of ELO-oxalic acid system. Heating rate of 5°C/min.

Table 6 presents the information related to ΔH , T_{peak} , and T_{onset} of ELO curing with oxalic acid. Due to the overlap between the exothermic curing peak and the endothermic water evaporation peak, an accurate calculation of the ΔH was not possible. Therefore, similar to the case of citric acid, these two peaks were separated using the same analytical approach, and the ΔH was estimated accordingly. The result of this peak separation is shown in [Figure 30 \(right\)](#).

Table 6. Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) for curing of ELO with oxalic acid.

Catalyst and concentration	ΔH (J/g)	T_{peak} (°C)	T_{onset} (°C)	T_g (°C)
Oxalic acid 27% wt.	201.08	74.5	56.9	3.93

Glass transition temperature of the thermoset obtained from curing ELO with oxalic acid was obtained by subjecting the cured polymer to DSC analysis in the temperature range of -20-170°C. The resulting thermogram is shown in [Figure 31](#). The transition corresponding to T_g – appears as a step change accompanied by a small peak – occurs at ca. 4°C ([Table 6](#)). This indicates that T_g of the thermoset produced with oxalic acid is slightly lower than that of the sample cured with citric acid. Nevertheless, the thermosets derived from these two acids exhibit a significantly higher T_g (approximately 20-30°C higher) compared to the thermosets produced by $Al(OTf)_3$ and BCF catalysts. This demonstrates that the thermoset possesses substantially higher stiffness than those obtained with the mentioned catalysts.

The glass transition behavior of oxalic acid system demonstrates a step change accompanied by a small peak, while in many other cases this peak is absent and only the step change appears, similar to the citric acid sample. Unlike the citric acid case, no peak corresponding to the curing reaction was detected, which proves that negligible amount of unreacted oxalic acid remained in the system.

Figure 31. DSC thermogram of cured ELO with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of 5°C/min.

FTIR analysis was performed to study the curing reaction of ELO with oxalic acid. As shown in [Figure 32](#), this test was conducted on pure oxalic acid, on a mixture of oxalic acid and ELO (with an acid-to-epoxy group ratio of 1:1) before curing, and on the same mixture after curing for 1.5 h at 60°C. The measurement conditions were identical to those used for citric acid sample, and the spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–450 cm⁻¹.

Figure 32. FTIR spectra of pure oxalic acid, ELO and oxalic acid mixture before curing and cured ELO with oxalic acid.

The main peaks in the FTIR spectrum of pure oxalic acid was the broad peak corresponding to the stretching vibration of hydroxyl groups identified at 3400 cm⁻¹. The characteristic peak at 1685 cm⁻¹, associated with the stretching vibrations of carbonyl (C=O) groups in the carboxylic acid groups is also clearly observable in this spectrum and similar to that of citric acid, [Figure 21](#). The important peaks of ELO-carboxylic acid mixture before curing were discussed in the section related to citric acid, [Figure 21](#). Here, only the peaks that change during the curing reaction are addressed. The hydroxyl peak at 3500 cm⁻¹, which appears with low intensity

corresponds to the hydroxyl groups present in oxalic acid. Another peak is the one at 821 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to the epoxy groups in the ELO structure.

In the spectrum of the cured thermoset, the changes in these two peaks are clearly visible. The hydroxyl peak increases in intensity, indicating that an epoxy ring-opening reaction with the carboxylic acid groups has taken place. Formation of new hydroxyl groups during the reaction leads to this increase. In contrast, the intensity of the epoxy peak decreases significantly, showing that these groups have been consumed; essentially, this peak disappears after curing. It is difficult to make a precise assessment regarding the unreacted oxalic acid remaining in the thermoset, because the shoulder on the ester carbonyl peak (at 1740 cm^{-1}) cannot be easily distinguished. Since the reaction mechanism of oxalic and citric acid is similar, further details on the FTIR interpretation are referred to the FTIR discussion in the citric acid section.

5.3.2 Mechanical properties and thermal resistance of thermosets with oxalic acid

To evaluate the mechanical properties of the thermoset obtained from the ELO-oxalic acid system, tensile testing was performed. The testing conditions, equipment used, and sample preparation procedures were identical with those described previously for citric acid, $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts. The tensile strength of the thermoset sample was 3.56 MPa , which is a value similar to that of citric acid thermoset sample (4.11 MPa) and significantly higher than the samples prepared with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and BCF catalysts. The elongation at break for this sample is 30% , (23% for the citric acid sample), indicating that the thermoset exhibited high ductility. Overall, all mechanical properties obtained for the thermoset cured with oxalic acid show good consistency and reproducibility compared to the citric acid system.

TGA analysis was carried out in the temperature range of $0\text{--}600^\circ\text{C}$ to evaluate the thermal stability of the thermoset obtained from ELO and oxalic acid. The test conditions were identical to those for the citric acid sample, with a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. [Figure 33](#) and [Table 7](#) present the results of the TGA analysis.

Figure 33. TGA graph of cured ELO with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Table 7. T_5 , T_{max} and residual weight at 600°C of a sample cured with oxalic acid (with a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups).

Hardener and concentration	T_5 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	T_{max} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Residual weight at 600°C (%)
Oxalic acid, 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups	154	409	1.20

Based on [Figure 33](#) and [Table 7](#), T_5 value was 154°C , which corresponds to loss of moisture and volatile compounds. Compared to the citric acid sample, T_5 of the oxalic acid system is higher, which may be related to the use of anhydrous oxalic acid, while citric acid is a monohydrate. However, it is evident that T_5 is not directly related to the thermal stability of the polymer network. Another significant weight loss occurs at 188°C , which can be attributed to the thermal decomposition of unreacted oxalic acid remaining in the system, as the melting point of oxalic acid lies in this range and coincides with its decomposition temperature. It should be noted that

this weight loss is smaller than the corresponding loss caused by the thermal decomposition of citric acid (Figure 23), indicating that a smaller amount of unreacted oxalic acid remains in the system compared to citric acid. The maximum rate of thermal decomposition is associated with ester bond cleavage and decomposition of the polymer network occurs at 409°C, i.e., a value similar to that of citric acid sample (410°C). The residual mass at 600°C is higher than that of the citric acid sample, measuring 1.2%. Overall, the thermal performance of oxalic and citric acid systems is similar. The thermal stability of oxalic and citric acid as binders are suitable for manufacturing composites containing wood particles.

5.3.3 Processing of wood composites with oxalic acid as hardener

Considering the suitable physical-mechanical performance of the ELO–oxalic acid thermoset and based on the experience gained from producing composites by using citric acid as hardener, the oxalic-acid-based composites were prepared directly using powdered oxalic acid and impregnated Scots pine particles with ethyl palmitate, without repeating the steps already described for preparation of wood composites with citric acid. A composite containing 50% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust particles, 7% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 43% wt. binder was prepared. The mass fraction of oxalic acid in the binder mixture was set to 25%. The processing of the composite started by mixing the impregnated Scots pine particles and wood fibers; after achieving a uniform mixture, fine powdered oxalic acid was added and mixing was continued. ELO was added and the blend was mixed until a homogeneous composition was obtained. The resulting blend was molded and pressed using the same equipment and procedure employed for the composites with citric acid and then placed in an oven at 75°C for 1.5 h (Figure 34a) and the same composition cured at 60°C for 1.5 h (Figure 34b).

Figure 34. Composite containing 50% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust particles, 7% wt. untreated CTMP birch fibers, and 43% wt. binder (ELO and oxalic acid, 75:25 ratio) cured at 75°C for 1.5 h (a) and at 60°C for 1.5 h (b).

Both composites exhibited an integrated structure and good mechanical strength. Using oxalic acid as hardener ensures a significant reduction of the curing temperature from 120 to 60°C.

An additional composite containing 60% impregnated Scots pine particles, 8% CTMP birch fibers, and 32% binder (composed of 75% wt. ELO and 25% wt. oxalic acid). The composite was cured at 60°C for 1.5 h and demonstrated a proper, well-integrated structure and good mechanical strength. Therefore, when low-temperature processing is of priority, oxalic acid can be considered an effective bio-hardener.

6. Properties of wood composites with citric and oxalic acids as hardeners

6.1 Physical-mechanical properties

An extensive study on the bio-composites' physical-mechanical properties is ongoing in WP4, Deliverable 4.5. Herewith some preliminary tests of composites with and without ethyl palmitate were carried out. Based on the results of curing and processability of composites with citric and oxalic acids, formulations consisting of 55% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust, 13% wt. untreated fibers, and 32% wt. ELO binder and citric or oxalic acid as catalysts were tested. Control composites without ethyl palmitate, consisting of 38% wt. untreated Scots pine sawdust, 18% wt. wood fibers and 44% wt. ELO binder with citric and oxalic acids as catalysts were tested as well. The results are presented in [Table 8](#).

Table 8. Physical-mechanical properties of composite with 55% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust, 13% wt. wood fibers, and 32% wt. ELO binder with citric or oxalic acids as catalysts. Control samples with 38% wt. untreated Scots pine sawdust, 18% wt. wood fibers and 44% wt. ELO binder with the same catalysts. Standard deviations within parentheses.

Composites	MOR, N/mm ²	MOE, N/mm ²	Internal bonding, N/mm ²	Water absorption, %	Swelling in thickness after 24 h, %
<i>Standards EN 312:2010 and 317:1993</i>	10.5	–	0.28	–	17
Composite with bioPCM, ELO + citric acid	2.4 (0.7)	317.5 (37.2)	0.19 (0.07)	49.1 (5.6)	13.2 (1.0)
Control composite ELO + citric acid	2.1 (0.5)	379.3 (50.9)	0.33 (0.03)	64.7 (10.6)	11.2 (0.7)
Composite with bioPCM, ELO + oxalic acid	4.2 (1.2)	597.3 (41.1)	0.22 (0.06)	16.9 (1.9)	6.2 (1.4)
Control composite ELO + oxalic acid	3.0 (0.5)	623.8 (74.8)	0.48 (0.18)	26.4 (5.9)	5.6 (1.0)

Recommended values are taken from standard EN 312:2010 “Particleboards – Specifications” where requirements for general purpose boards for use in dry conditions (Type P1) were selected. Modulus of rupture (MOR) and elasticity (MOE) were determined according to standard EN 310:1993. Internal bonding was measured according to standard EN 319:1993. Water absorption and swelling in thickness were determined in accordance with standard EN 317:1993.

There are no explicit limits for MOE, water absorption (mass increase) and swelling in thickness for particleboards Type P1 according to EN 312. Density is a parameter that can be regulated easily; the composites in [Table 8](#) have density in the interval 850-900 kg/m³. The density of the composites with ELO binder was higher than the density of the composites with lignosulfonates as binder reported in Deliverable 3.2.

When the bending strength (MOR) of the composites is compared to the recommended value in the standard EN 312 for general purpose boards, (10.5 N/mm²) it is significantly lower and in the range 2.1-4.2 N/mm² regardless the used hardener. MOE is also low, somewhat higher in the control composites without bioPCM. The advantage of using ELO as binder is the increased hydrophobicity of the material with swelling in the thickness significantly less than the 17%-value of recommendation in standard EN 317. Water absorption is also low, in particular for the composites with oxalic acid binder (16.9-26.4%). Internal bonding in the control composites without ethyl palmitate is higher than the recommended value in standard EN 312 and lower than that when the particles impregnated with bioPCM are added. Oxalic acid demonstrated higher internal bonding

than citric acid hardener. Apparently and based on the preliminary results, oxalic acid is better hardener than citric acid. Addition of impregnated particles decreases the mechanical properties due to insufficient adhesion between the binder and particles with oily surfaces. Another advantage of using oxalic acid is that the curing temperature can be reduced to 60°C. It should also be noted that the laboratory-scale cost of oxalic acid is similar to that of citric acid. The two composites with citric and oxalic acid demonstrated that curing ELO with small-molecule, multifunctional bio-hardeners must be upscaled at pilot plant level (Deliverable 4.3).

Stability of the impregnated ethyl palmitate is good; no leaching was observed after 30 days exposure at 50°C temperature in an oven. However, crystallization of ethyl palmitate on the board's surface must be eliminated. Crystallization does not mean leaching of the bioPCM, it is a surface phenomenon that is an aesthetic problem and probably can influence the finishing of the boards by lamination or painting.

6.2 Thermal properties

Figures 35 and 37 show respectively the temperature profile vs. time for wood composites containing bioPCM and using citric and oxalic acid as hardeners, while Figures 36 and 38 are calculated enthalpy based on the reported temperature behavior of the composites. As seen in Figures 35 and 37, the composite with citric acid showed a more stable temperature profile while the composite made of oxalic as hardener showed two solidification patterns during cooling. On the other hand, composites with oxalic acid as hardener showed a more uniform and sharper pattern compared to composites with citric acid during heating. The processing difference between the two composites is in the curing temperature, which is 70°C for oxalic and 120°C for citric acid. The effect of this can be clearly seen on the enthalpy of the composites, with a melting enthalpy of the composite made with citric acid of 40 J/g and 68 J/g for the composite with oxalic acid as hardener. This can be explained by the fact that the higher curing temperature of citric acid may cause leaching of the bioPCM during the process. It is also observed that the temperature of melting/solidification of the bioPCM in the composites is in the range of 17-24°C, being slightly higher for composites with oxalic acid than citric acid the hardener. The melting temperature of the pure ethyl palmitate used as bioPCM is 25°C, showing that the working temperature of the composites with oxalic is closer to that of pure bioPCM, thus justifying the use of oxalic acid as hardener to improve the thermal performance of the composite. Additionally, processing the composite at lower curing temperature facilitates the technology and cost of the product.

Figure 35. Thermal behavior of wood-bioPCM composite with citric acid as hardener.

Figure 36. Enthalpy vs. temperature of wood-bioPCM composites with citric acid as hardener.

Figure 37. Thermal behavior of wood-bioPCM composite with oxalic acid as hardener.

Figure 38. Enthalpy vs. temperature of wood-bioPCM composite with oxalic acid as hardener.

7. Curing of ELO by UV photo-polymerization

Considering the risk of bioPCM leaching from the bio-composites, a need of surface treatment was predicted in the stage of writing the project proposal. Indeed, due to the hydrophilic nature of wood and the hydrophobic nature of the PCM, as well as processing parameters during composite processing, e.g., temperature and pressure, the impregnated ethyl palmitate can crystallise on the composite surface (Figure 39). The above shows that an additional layer of polymer (coating) capable of curing at ambient temperature can encapsulate the surface and stop the migration of bioPCM. An example can be a solvent-based coating composed of ELO and oxalic acid. The oxalic acid was first dissolved in ethanol and added to ELO. The homogenised mixture was applied with a brush to the composite (Figure 39). This coating system was able to cure at ambient temperature. However, increasing the curing temperature accelerates the reaction and may also improve the mechanical properties of the final coating.

It is worth noting that dissolving oxalic acid in a protic solvent (i. e. ethanol) not only reduced the viscosity of the system but also ensured molecular-level dispersion of the oxalic acid, providing uniform availability for reaction with the epoxy groups of ELO. As a result, this coating system was able to cure at ambient temperature.

Figure 39. Crystalization of ethyl palmitate on the surface of the composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles, and a binder of ELO with oxalic acid. Bio-composite after processing (left), after storage (middle) and with ELO-oxalic acid coating (shiny surface at right). The composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles and a binder of ELO with oxalic acid.

The limitation of the above approach and other curing systems with polymerization initiated by a thermal stimulus is the short pot life and the onset of polymerization during the mixing and application stages. Therefore,

another category of coatings that cure at ambient temperature by UV photo polymerisation when it is initiated by ultraviolet within a specific wavelength range [37].

In UV-curing coating formulations, a photo initiator decomposes into reactive species upon exposure to UV radiation of a specific wavelength. These species subsequently initiate the polymerization of monomers within the system. Depending on the type of monomer involved, photo initiators are classified into two categories, i.e., suitable for radical and cationic polymerization [38-40]. UV radiation is a region of the electromagnetic spectrum spanning wavelengths from 100 to 400 nm. It is typically divided into the bands of UV-A (320-400 nm), UV-B (280-320 nm), and UV-C (100-280 nm) [42]. UV-curing coatings are regarded as environmentally friendly from an energy perspective due to their high efficiency (characterized by short curing times and absence of thermal energy requirements) [41]. In addition, the lack of heat during the curing process enables their application on temperature-sensitive substrates such as paper, plastics [37], and the bio-composites of interest of the project.

7.1 UV-curing based on free-radical polymerization

Radical polymerization occurs in coatings when UV radiation is absorbed by a photo initiator, which is decomposed into free radicals. The radicals subsequently initiate polymerization in the presence of vinyl monomers, such as acrylates, leading to formation of a polymer film [43, 44]. Photo initiators used in this class of systems are divided into two groups: unimolecular and bimolecular types [45, 46].

Unimolecular photo initiators, referred to as Norrish type I initiators, undergo homolytic cleavage upon absorption of UV radiation, producing two free radicals [47], as illustrated in Figure 40. The cleavage in this type of photo initiators is alpha, although in some cases beta cleavage may also take place.

Figure 40. Example of a unimolecular photo initiator used for radical polymerization and free radicals generated through UV-induced cleavage [37].

Unimolecular photo initiators used for radical polymerization are 2-hydroxy-2-methylpropiophenone [48, 49], diphenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphine oxide [47, 48], 2-hydroxy-4'-(2-hydroxyethoxy)-2-methylpropiophenone [37, 48] and ethyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phenylphosphinate [48, 50].

Bimolecular photo initiators, referred to as Norrish type II initiators, do not undergo bond scission to generate free radicals under UV irradiation due to their high bond dissociation energy [44]. Instead, UV exposure excites the photo initiator, which abstracts a hydrogen atom from a hydrogen-donor compound in the system. This process leads to formation of free radicals [37, 51-53], as illustrated in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Example of a bimolecular photo initiator used for radical polymerization [37].

Bimolecular photo initiators for radical polymerization are 2,4-Diethyl-9H-thioxanthen-9-one, methyl 2-benzoylbenzoate and 4-phenylbenzophenone [54].

Since curing ELO proceeds through cationic ring-opening polymerization rather than radical polymerization, this class of photo initiators (either unimolecular or bimolecular) cannot be directly used to cure ELO. One proposed

approach to overcome this limitation is the vinylation of ELO using vinyl monomers such as acrylic acid (Figure 42). The epoxy groups of ELO react with the vinyl monomer, introducing the vinyl functionalities required for radical polymerization. The resulting modified ELO can then be cured using the photo initiators discussed above [55-59].

Figure 42. Vinylation of ELO using vinyl monomers.

A disadvantage of this approach is that it requires additional chemical modification using non-bio-based compounds such as acrylic acid or other vinyl monomers. This increases production costs and reduces the bio-based content of the final product. A possible alternative solution is the use of cationic polymerization photo initiators.

7.2 UV-curing based on cationic polymerization

Photo initiators suitable for cationic polymerization generate a Brønsted acid upon absorption of UV radiation. The acid initiates the curing of epoxy resins through a cationic ring-opening polymerization mechanism. The curing rate of cationic UV systems is lower than that of radical-based systems [60]. However, an advantage is their lower sensitivity to atmospheric oxygen [37]. The initiation mechanism for this class of photo initiators is illustrated in Figure 43 [61-63]. Table 9 presents the structures of some photo initiators.

Figure 43. Example of a photo initiator used for cationic polymerization and Brønsted acid generated through UV irradiation.

Two photo initiators, *triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts* (mixed) and *bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate*, were selected to cure ELO as a bio-based coating to prevent crystallisation/leakage of bioPCM from the composite. Triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) are liquids soluble in ELO, that can be used without a solvent at a concentration of 3 wt.%, consistent with values reported in the literature [28-31]. After stirring to a homogeneous mixture, the coating was applied to solid wood (thermally modified pine) using a brush to evaluate the performance of the photo initiator. The coated surface was then exposed to UV radiation (Figure 44) by a LED lamp with a peak emission wavelength of 365 nm and a power of approximately 0.5 W/cm². The distance between the sample surface and the lamp was 3 cm.

Table 9. Chemical structures of bimolecular photo initiators used for radical polymerization.

Name	Chemical structure
Triarylsulfonium hexafluorophosphate salts [37]	
(4-(Octyloxy)phenyl)(phenyl)iodonium hexafluorostibate(V) [59, 64]	
Bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate	
4-Thiophenyl phenyl diphenyl sulfonium hexafluoroantimonate [65]	
Triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts, mixed [37]	

Figure 44. UV radiation source and sample (left) positioning during UV exposure. Uncoated thermally modified pine wood (middle) and a sample with UV-curable ELO coating (right).

The curing process was applied to a wood composite with impregnated particles. The application on this substrate was also successful (Figure 45).

Figure 45. Biocomposite without coating (left), composite with one layer of UV-cured coating (middle), and composite with two layers of UV-cured coating (right). The composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles, and a binder of ELO with citric acid.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was applied to the coating mixture before and after curing with UV radiation. The results are shown in [Figure 46](#).

Figure 46. FTIR spectra of UV-curable coating composed of ELO and triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) photo initiator before and after curing.

As shown in [Figure 46](#), the peak at approximately 821 cm^{-1} , associated with vibration of epoxy groups, is present in the uncured coating while the peak disappears after curing, indicating the consumption of epoxy rings during the polymerization reaction [68-70]. Another significant peak appears at around 1072 cm^{-1} and corresponds to the stretching vibration of linear ether bonds [27]. This peak exhibit high intensity in the cured ELO, indicating the extensive formation of linear ether linkages because of the curing reaction. Additional FTIR features also support the occurrence of curing, such as the increased intensity of the hydroxyl stretching band around 3450 cm^{-1} in the cured ELO.

Bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate in powder form was dissolved in acetone, and the solution then added to ELO. The prepared mixture was applied to the wood composite by brushing. Compared to the triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) photo initiator, the curing process with this photo initiator was slower and required approximately 10 min of UV irradiation to achieve curing and setting. After the exposure time, a uniform and solid coating was formed on the composite surface.

[Figure 47](#) shows the characteristic epoxy vibration peak at 821 cm^{-1} , which disappeared after curing, indicating successful consumption of epoxy groups and confirming effective cationic polymerization of ELO. Similarly to the system containing triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed), the appearance of a peak at approximately 1074 cm^{-1} , associated with the stretching vibration of linear ether bonds, and the increased

intensity of the hydroxyl stretching band in the cured coating (3450 cm^{-1}) confirmed ELO curing reaction in the presence of bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate.

Figure 47. FTIR spectra of UV-curable coating composed of ELO and bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate photoinitiator before and after curing.

The obtained results lead to the conclusion that UV-curable coatings formulated with ELO with either triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) or bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate enable low-temperature curing, providing essentially unlimited pot life, and maintain a high bio-based content. Consequently, these coating systems represent suitable options for coating of bio-based composites to prevent crystallization or leaching of bioPCM.

8. Conclusions and recommendations for pilot-plant upscaling

Considering the experimental and theoretical studies done for screening of appropriate catalysts and hardeners for curing ELO and production of wood-bioPCM composites, the results were summarized in **Figure 48**. As shown in this figure, the hardeners and catalysts were evaluated based on several criteria, including bio-based content, curing time and temperature, physical-mechanical, thermal properties, and cost. The comparison clearly indicated that citric and oxalic acid satisfy the project requirements. Therefore, these two compounds were selected as hardeners for producing bioPCM-containing composites at a pilot scale (see Deliverable D4.3 “Demonstration of wallboard production”). It is important to note that the component ratios in the particleboard formulation, as well as the curing conditions in the pilot scale, were determined based on the laboratory findings presented in this Deliverable 3.1.

Figure 48. Evaluation of the performance of catalysts and hardeners for curing ELO based on five key criteria.

Working temperature of the bioPCM-wood composites with oxalic was closer to that of pure bioPCM and a melting enthalpy of ca. 70 J/g justified the use of oxalic acid as hardener to improve the thermal performance of the composite. Additionally, processing the composite at lower curing temperature facilitates the technology and cost of the product.

Preliminary physical-mechanical results demonstrated that oxalic acid is better hardener than citric acid. Addition of impregnated particles decreases the mechanical properties due to insufficient adhesion between the binder and particles with oily surfaces. Another advantage of using oxalic acid is that the curing temperature is 60°C. Stability of the impregnated ethyl palmitate is good; no leaching was observed after 30-days exposure at 50°C temperature. However, crystallization of ethyl palmitate on the board's surface must be eliminated. Crystallization does not mean leaching of the bioPCM, it is a surface phenomenon that is an aesthetic problem and probably can influence the finishing of the boards by lamination or painting. In order to eliminate crystallization of bioPCM, UV-curable coatings with ELO and either triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) or bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate photo initiators enabled low-temperature curing.

Following the laboratory results, SLU is prepared for the coming work in WP4 where the scale-up of the composite production demands ca. 180 kg ELO binder, provided with guidelines and safety instructions. SLU has collaborated with the project partner BOKU by sharing experience in analytical analyses and characterization of the plant oil-based binders. The results of Task 3.1, presented in Deliverable 3.1, are conveyed and used further in Task 3.4 in WP3 and Tasks 4.1-4.4 in the work of WP4.

References

- [1] Xia, Y., Larock, R., C. (2010) Vegetable oil-based polymeric materials: synthesis, properties, and applications. *Green Chemistry* 12:1893-1909.
- [2] Williams, C., K., Hillmyer, M., A. (2008) Polymers from renewable resources: A perspective for a special issue of polymer reviews, *Polymer Reviews* 48(1):1-10.
- [3] Huber, G., W., Iborra, S., Corma, A. (2006) Synthesis of transportation fuels from biomass: chemistry, catalysts, and engineering, *Chemical Reviews* 106(9):4044-4098.
- [4] Baroncini, E., a., Kumar Yadav, S., Palmese, G., R., Stanzione III, J., F. (2016) Recent advances in bio-based epoxy resins and bio-based epoxy curing agents. *J. of Applied Polymer Sci.* 133(45):1-19.
- [5] Zhang, C, Garrison, T., F., Madbouly, S., I., Kessler, M., R. (2017) Recent advances in vegetable oil-based polymers and their composites. *Progress in Polymer Science* 71:91-143.
- [6] Belgacem, M., N., Gandini, A. (Eds.) (2011) Monomers, polymers and composites from renewable resources. Elsevier.
- [7] Pfister, D., P., Xia, Y., Larock, R., C. (2011) Recent advances in vegetable oil-based polyurethanes, *ChemSusChem* 4(6):703-717.
- [8] Meier, M., A., R., Metzger, J., O., Schubert, U., S. (2007) Plant oil renewable resources as green alternatives in polymer science. *Chemical Society Reviews* 36:1788-1802.
- [9] Li, F., Larock, R., C. (2003) Synthesis, structure and properties of new tung oil-styrene-divinylbenzene copolymers prepared by thermal polymerization. *Biomacromolecules* 4(4):1018-1025.
- [10] Mauro, C., D., Malburet, S., Genua, A., Graillot, A., Mija, A. (2020) Sustainable series of new epoxidized vegetable oil-based thermosets with chemical recycling properties. *Biomacromolecules* 21(9):3923-3935.
- [11] Kaikade, D., S., Sabnis, A., S. (2023) Polyurethane foams from vegetable oil-based polyols: a review. *Polymer Bulletin* 80:2239-2261.
- [12] Thiele, K., Eversmann, N., Krombholz, A., Pufky-Heinrich, D. (2019) Bio-based epoxy resins based on linseed oil cured with naturally occurring acids. *Polymers* 11(9):1409.
- [13] Boquillon, N., Fringant, C. (2000) Polymer networks derived from curing of epoxidized linseed oil: influence of different catalysts and anhydride hardeners. *Polymer* 41(24):8603-8613.
- [14] Supanchaiyamat, N., Shuttleworth, P., S., Hunt, A., J., Clark, J., H., Matharu, A., S. (2012) Thermosetting resin based on epoxidized linseed oil and bio-derived crosslinker. *Green Chemistry* 14:1759-1765.
- [15] Todorovic, A., Resch-Fauster, K., Mahendran, A., R., Oreski, G., Kern, W. (2021) Curing of epoxidized linseed oil: Investigation of the curing reaction with different hardener types. *J. of Applied Polymer Science* 38(16):50239.
- [16] España, J., M., Sánchez-Nacher, L., Boronat, T., Fombuena, V., Balart, R. (2012) Properties of biobased epoxy resins from epoxidized soybean oil (ESBO) cured with maleic anhydride (MA). *J. of the American Oil Chemists' Society* 89:2067-2075.
- [17] Pin, J.-M., Sbirrazzuoli, M., Mija, A. (2015) From epoxidized linseed oil to bioresin: An overall approach of epoxy/anhydride cross-linking. *ChemSusChem* 8(7):1232-1243.

- [18] Espinoza-Perez, J., D., Nerenz, B., A., Haagenson, D., M., Chen, Z., Ulven, C., A., Wiesenborn, D., P. (2011) Comparison of curing agents for epoxidized vegetable oils applied to composites. *Polymer Composites* 32(11):1806-1816.
- [19] Chakrapani, S., Crivello, J., V. (1998) Synthesis and photoinitiated cationic polymerization of epoxidized castor oil and its derivatives. *J. of Macromolecular Science Part A* 35(1):1-20.
- [20] Yang, Z., Narayanan, J., Ravalli, M., Rupp, B., T., Ryu, C., Y. (2017) Structure-property relationships of epoxy thermoset networks from photoinitiated cationic polymerization of epoxidized vegetable oils. In: C. Tang, C. Y. Ryu, (Eds.) *Sustainable polymers from biomass*. Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co:209-226.
- [21] Tran, T-N., Di Mauro, C., Graillot, A., Mija, A. (2020) Monitoring the structure–reactivity relationship in epoxidized perilla and safflower oil thermosetting resins. *Polymer Chemistry* 11:5088-5097.
- [22] Li, M., Jiang, N., Guo, G., Lu, S., Li, Z., Mu, Y., Xia, X., Xu, Z., Hu, Y., Xiang, X. (2024) Perilla seed oil: A review of health effects, encapsulation strategies and applications in food. *Foods* 13(22):3615.
- [23] Dąbrowski, G., Tańska, M., Czaplicki, S., Sadowski, T., Rychcik, B., Kostrzewska, M., K., Antoszkiewicz, Z., Konopka, I. (2025) Variation in linseed oil composition: Impact of cultivar, cultivation system, and year of cultivation. *Molecules* 30(4):875.
- [24] Jian, X-Y., An, X-P., Li, Y-D., Chen, J-H., Wang, M., Zeng, J-B. (2017) All plant oil derived epoxy thermosets with excellent comprehensive properties. *Macromolecules* 50(15): 5729-5738.
- [25] Márquez, E., D., Santiago, E., V., López, S., H. (2019) Thermal study of aluminum trifluoromethyl sulfonate as effective catalyst for the polymerization of epoxidized linseed oil. *Physical Chemistry* 9(1):1-7.
- [26] Jin, F., L., Park, S-J. (2007) Thermal and rheological properties of vegetable oil-based epoxy resins cured with thermally latent initiator. *J. of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 13(5):808-814.
- [27] Petrović, Z., S., Hong, J., Vuković, M., L., Djonlajić, J. (2022) Epoxy resins and composites from epoxidized linseed oil copolymers with cyclohexene oxide. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology* 39:102269.
- [28] International Standard ISO 527-2 (2012) *Plastics — Determination of tensile properties – Part 2: Test conditions for moulding and extrusion plastics*.
- [29] Kunioka, M., Wang, Y., Onozawa, S-Y. (2005) Poly(lactic acid) polymerized by aluminum triflate, *Macromolecular Symposia* 224(1):167-180.
- [30] Patry, S., Asseray, A., Berne, M., Lorient, V., Lorient, L., Habas, J-P. (2025) Structure-property relationships in epoxy-anhydride systems: A comprehensive comparative study of cycloaliphatic, novolac, and aromatic prepolymers. *Polymers* 17(21):2843.
- [31] Pavarelli, G., Velasquez, J., Ochoa, A., Caldarelli, F., Puzzo, F., Cavani, J-L., Dubois, A. (2015) New process for maleic anhydride synthesis from a renewable building block: The gas-phase oxidehydration of bio-1-butanol. *ChemSusChem* 8(13):2250-2259.
- [32] Cucciniello, R., Cespi, D., Riccardi, M., Neri, E., Passarini, E., Pulselli, F., M. (2023) Maleic anhydride from bio-based 1-butanol and furfural: a life cycle assessment at the pilot scale, *Green Chemistry* 25:5922-5935.
- [33] Tanaka, Y., Bauer, R., S. (1988) Curing reactions, In: C. A. May, (Ed) *Epoxy resins: Chemistry and technology revised and expanded*, Marcel Dekker Inc.:285-464.
- [34] Nameer, S., Johansson, M. (2017) Fully bio-based aliphatic thermoset polyesters via self-catalysed self-condensation of multifunctional epoxy monomers directly extracted from natural sources, *J. of Coatings Tech. and Research* 14:757-765.
- [35] Lodi, L., A., Klaić, R., Bortoletto-Santos, R., Ribeiro, C., Farinas, C., S. (2022) Unveiling the solubilization of potassium mineral rocks in organic acids for application as K-Fertilizer. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology* 194:2431-2447.
- [36] Nazari, M., Jebrane, M., Terziev, N. (2023) New hybrid bio-composite based on epoxidized linseed oil and wood particles hosting ethyl palmitate for energy storage in buildings. *Energy*, Vol. 278, 127692, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127692>.
- [37] Patil, r., S., Thomas, J., Patil, M., John, J. (2023) To shed light on the UV curable coating technology: Current state of the art and perspectives, *J. of Composites Science* 7, 12, 513.
- [38] Shukla, V., Bajpai, M., Singh, D., K., Singh, M., Shukla, S. (2004) Review of basic chemistry of UV-curing technology. *Pigment & Resin Technology* 33, 5, 272-279.
- [39] Decker, C. (1998) The use of UV irradiation in polymerization. *Polymer International* 45, 2, 133-141.
- [40] Lazare, S., Granier, V. (1989) Ultraviolet laser photoablation of polymers: A review and recent results. *Laser Chemistry* 10, 25-40.
- [41] Su, Y., Zhang, S., Zhou, X., Yang, Z., Yuan, T. (2000) A novel multi-functional bio-based reactive diluent derived from cardanol for high bio-content UV-curable coatings application. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 148, 105880.
- [42] Javadi, A., Mehr, H., S., Sobani, M., Soucek, M., D. (2016) Cure-on-command technology: A review of the current state of the art. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 100, 2-31.

- [43] Schwalm, R. (2007) UV coatings: basics, recent developments and new applications, Elsevier Ltd.
- [44] Green, W., A. (2010) Industrial photoinitiators: A technical guide, CRC Press.
- [45] Lee, Z-H., Yen, S-C., Hammoud, F., Hijazi, A., Graff, B., Lalevée, J., Chen, Y-C. (2022) Naphthalene-based oxime esters as type I photoinitiators for free radical photopolymerization. *Polymers* 14, 23, 5261.
- [46] Hageman, H., J. (1985) Photoinitiators for free radical polymerization. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 13, 2, 123-150.
- [47] Kowalska, A., Sokolowski, J., Bociong, K. (2021) The photoinitiators used in resin based dental composite— A review and future perspectives. *Polymers* 13, 3, 470.
- [48] Maurel, A., Martinez, A., C., Grugeon, S., Panier, S., Dupont, L., Cortes, P., Sherrard, C., J., Small, I., Sreenivasan, S., T., Macdonald, E. (2021) Toward high 3D printing of shape-conformable batteries via vat photopolymerization: Review and perspective, *IEEE Access* 9, 140654-140666.
- [49] Molina-Gutiérrez, S., Dalle Vacche, S., Vitale, A., Ladmiral, V., Caillol, S., Bongiovanni, R., Lacroix-Desmazes, P. (2020) Photoinduced polymerization of eugenol-derived methacrylates. *Molecules* 25, 3444.
- [50] Wu, Y., Dai, C., Ke, J., Tang, R., Huang, C., Wang, J., Situ, Y., Huang, H. (2023) Synthesis and characterization of low-migration bisacylphenylphosphine oxide photoinitiators. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 176, 107396.
- [51] Lalevée, J., El-Roz, M., Allonas, X., Fouassier, J-P. (2009) Surface modification of a UV curable acrylate coating: In situ introduction of hydrophobic properties. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 65, 4, 457-461.
- [52] Huang, T-L., Chen, Y-C. (2022) Synthesis and free radical photopolymerization of one-component type II photoinitiator based on benzophenone segment. *J. of Photochemistry and Photobiology A* 429, 113900.
- [53] Balta, D., K., Keskin, S., Karasu, F., A., Arsu, N. (2007) Quinoxaline derivatives as photoinitiators in UV-cured coatings. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 60, 3, 207-210.
- [54] Balcerak, A., Kabatc-Borcz, J., Czech, Z., Bartkowiak, M. (2023) Latest advances in highly efficient dye-based photoinitiating systems for radical polymerization. *Polymers* 15, 1148.
- [55] Sahoo, S., K., Khandelwal, V., Manik, G. (2019) Synthesis and characterization of low viscous and highly acrylated epoxidized methyl ester based green adhesives derived from linseed oil, *Int. J. Adhesion and Adhesives* 89, 174-177.
- [56] Su, Y., Zhang, S., Chen, Y., Yuan, T., Yang, Z. (2020) One-step synthesis of novel renewable multi-functional linseed oil-based acrylate prepolymers and its application in UV-curable coatings. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 148, 105820.
- [57] Saraswat, R., Shagun, A., Dhir, A., Balan, S., S., Powar, S., Doddamani, M. (2024) Synthesis and application of sustainable vegetable oil-based polymers in 3D printing. *RSC Sustainability* 2, 1708-1737.
- [58] Wuzella, G., Mahendran, A., R., Müller, U., Kandelbauer, A., Teischinger, A. (2012) Photocrosslinking of an acrylated epoxidized linseed oil: Kinetics and its application for optimized wood coatings. *J. of Polymers and Environment* 20, 1063-1074.
- [59] Li, Y., Wang, D., Sun, X., S. (2018) Epoxidized and acrylated epoxidized camelina oils for ultraviolet-curable wood coatings. *J. of the American Oil Chemists' Society* 95, 10, 1307-1318.
- [60] Thomas, J., Bouscher, R., F., Nwosu, J., Soucek, M., D. (2022) Sustainable thermosets and composites based on the epoxides of norbornylized seed oils and biomass fillers. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 10, 37, 12342-12354.
- [61] Crivello, J., V., Liu, S. (2000) Photoinitiated cationic polymerization of epoxy alcohol monomers. *J. Polymer Science Part A* 38, 3, 389-401.
- [62] Geisler, E., Lecomperre, M., Soppera, O. (2022) 3D printing of optical materials by processes based on photopolymerization: Materials, technologies, and recent advances. *Photonics Research* 10, 6, 1344-1360.
- [63] Crivello, J., V., (2009) Radical-promoted visible light photoinitiated cationic polymerization of epoxides. *J. Macromolecular Science Part A* 46, 5, 474-483.
- [64] Zong, Z., He, J., Soucek, M., D. (2005) UV-curable organic-inorganic hybrid films based on epoxynorbornene linseed oils. *Progress in Organic Coatings* 53, 2, 83-90.
- [65] Zou, K., Soucek, M., D. (2005) UV-curable cycloaliphatic epoxide based on modified linseed oil: Synthesis, characterization and kinetics. *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics* 206, 9, 967-975.
- [66] Crivello, J., V., Narayan, R. (1992) Epoxidized triglycerides as renewable monomers in photoinitiated cationic polymerization. *Chemistry of Materials* 4, 3, 692-699.
- [67] Shibata, M., Teramoto, N., Someya, Y., Suzuki, S. (2009) Bio-based nanocomposites composed of photo-cured epoxidized soybean oil and supramolecular hydroxystearic acid nanofibers. *J. Polymer Science* 47, 7, 669-673.
- [68] Márquez, E., D., Santiago, E., V., López, S., H. (2019) Thermal study of aluminum trifluoromethyl sulfonate as effective catalyst for the polymerization of epoxidized linseed oil. *Physical Chemistry* 9, 1-7.

- [69] Jebrane, M., Cai, S., Sandström, C., Terziev, N. (2017) The reactivity of linseed and soybean oil with different epoxidation degree towards vinyl acetate and impact of the resulting copolymer on the wood durability. *eXPRESS Polymer Letters* 11, 5, 383-395.
- [70] Janesch, J., Solt-Rindler, A., Dumschat, L., Vay, O., Mija, A., Gindl-Altmutter, W., Rosenau, T., Raffener, W., Hansmann, C. (2025) Flexible biobased thermosets from epoxidized plant oils: A study of aliphatic cross-linking agents. *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* 7, 6, 3686-3697.

List of Figures

Figure number	Title	Page
Figure 1	General structure of the vegetable oils (R_1 , R_2 , R_3 are aliphatic chains of different fatty acids)	7
Figure 2	General forms of reactions route and the raw materials used in the production of the most common biopolymers.	8
Figure 3	Chemical structure of phthalic anhydride and hexahydrophthalic anhydride.	9
Figure 4	Chemical structures of DGEBA and ELO, highlighting their key differences.	10
Figure 5	Two thermoset pieces made from ELO and $Al(OTf)_3$. The curing conditions are specified; the chemical structure of the catalyst is presented alongside a schematic representation of crosslinked ELO molecules.	11
Figure 6	Two thermoset samples composed of cured ELO by BCF. The curing conditions are detailed in the figure along with the chemical structure of the catalyst.	12
Figure 7	DSC thermograms of the ELO curing reaction with $Al(OTf)_3$ and BFC at two concentrations, alongside the DSC thermogram of ELO without catalyst. The heating rate was set at $5^\circ C/min$.	13
Figure 8	DSC thermograms of the cured ELO with BCF and $Al(OTf)_3$ at two concentrations. The heating rate was set at $5^\circ C/min$.	13
Figure 9	FTIR spectra of pure ELO and ELO cured with $Al(OTf)_3$ and BCF at two concentrations.	14
Figure 10	Foaming of ELO during the curing reaction at high concentrations of the catalysts BCF and	15
Figure 11	Aluminium mold (a) and dimensions of the specimen for mechanical tensile testing (b).	15
Figure 12	Tensile testing setup (a) and post-test specimens (b). From left to right in b): specimen cured with BCF at 0.66% wt., BCF at 0.31% wt., $Al(OTf)_3$ at 0.66% wt. and $Al(OTf)_3$ at 0.31% wt. concentrations.	16
Figure 13	Agglomerates of binder and wood particles with $Al(OTf)_3$ catalyst at 0.66% wt. (a) and an integrated composite using BCF catalyst (b).	17
Figure 14	Chemical structure of diphenylamine, a sample of ELO and diphenylamine after 20 h at $100^\circ C$, and another sample cured for 20 h at $180^\circ C$.	18
Figure 15	Chemical structure of 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid, a sample of ELO and 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid after 20 h at $100^\circ C$, and another sample cured for 20 h at $130^\circ C$.	19
Figure 16	Chemical structure of maleic anhydride, thermosets using this hardener and a schematic representation of ELO molecules crosslinked by maleic anhydride.	21
Figure 17	Chemical structure of citric acid, thermosets using this hardener and a schematic representation of ELO molecules crosslinked by citric acid.	22
Figure 18	Sample cured with 20% wt. citric acid and 2% wt. imidazole at $120^\circ C$ for 1.5 h.	23
Figure 19	DSC thermogram (a) of ELO curing reaction with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio and deconvolution of overlapping melting and curing peaks (b) of ELO-citric acid system. Heating rate of $5^\circ C/min$.	24
Figure 20	DSC thermogram of cured ELO with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of $5^\circ C/min$.	24
Figure 21	FTIR spectrums of pure citric acid, ELO and citric acid mixture before curing and cured ELO with citric acid.	25

Figure 22	Post-test specimens of ELO cured with citric acid (with a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups) at 120°C for 1.5 h and TGA graph of cured ELO with citric acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of 10°C/min.	26
Figure 23	Composite containing 33% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 17% wt. CTMP birch fibers and 50% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid) prepared in solution form.	27
Figure 24	Composites containing 33% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 17% wt. CTMP birch fibers and 50% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid). Citric acid solution was added to the wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.	28
Figure 25	Composite containing 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid. Citric acid solution was added to the wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.	28
Figure 26	Composite containing 46.5% wt. Scots pine sawdust, 23.3% wt. birch CTMP (chemical-thermomechanical pulp) fibers, 22.6% ELO and 7.6% citric acid. Citric acid fine powder was added to wood fibers prior to addition of ELO.	29
Figure 27	Composite containing 45% wt. impregnated Scots pine particles, 15% wt. CTMP birch fibers, and 40% wt. binder (ELO and citric acid, 75:25).	30
Figure 28	Composite containing 50% (a) and 60% (b) impregnated Scots pine particles.	30
Figure 29	Samples cured with 27% wt. oxalic acid in powder form at 60°C for 1.5 h.	31
Figure 30	DSC thermogram (a) of ELO curing reaction with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio and deconvolution of overlapping melting and curing peaks (b) of ELO-oxalic acid system. Heating rate of 5°C/min.	32
Figure 31	DSC thermogram of cured ELO with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of 5°C/min.	33
Figure 32	FTIR spectra of pure oxalic acid, ELO and oxalic acid mixture before curing and cured ELO with oxalic acid.	33
Figure 33	TGA graph of cured ELO with oxalic acid at a 1:1 epoxy-to-acid equivalent ratio. Heating rate of 10°C/min.	34
Figure 34	Composite containing 50% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust particles, 7% wt. untreated CTMP birch fibers, and 43% wt. binder (ELO and oxalic acid, 75:25 ratio) cured at 75°C for 1.5 h (a) and at 60°C for 1.5 h (b).	35
Figure 35	Thermal behavior of wood-bioPCM composite with citric acid as hardener.	37
Figure 36	Enthalpy vs. temperature of wood-bioPCM composites with citric acid as hardener.	38
Figure 37	Thermal behavior of wood-bioPCM composite with oxalic acid as hardener.	38
Figure 38	Enthalpy vs. temperature of wood-bioPCM composite with oxalic acid as hardener.	39
Figure 39	Crystallization of ethyl palmitate on the surface of the composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles, and a binder of ELO with oxalic acid. Bio-composite after processing (left), after storage (middle) and with ELO-oxalic acid coating (shiny surface at right). The composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles and a binder of ELO with oxalic acid.	39
Figure 40	Example of a unimolecular photo initiator used for radical polymerization and free radicals generated through UV-induced cleavage [1].	40
Figure 41	Example of a bimolecular photo initiator used for radical polymerization [1].	40
Figure 42	Vinylation of ELO using vinyl monomers.	41
Figure 43	Example of a photo initiator used for cationic polymerization and Brønsted acid generated through UV irradiation.	41
Figure 44	UV radiation source and sample (left) positioning during UV exposure. Uncoated thermally modified pine wood (middle) and a sample with UV-curable ELO coating (right).	42
Figure 45	Bio-composite without coating (left), composite with one layer of UV-cured coating (middle), and composite with two layers of UV-cured coating (right). The composite contained 55% impregnated pine particles, and a binder of ELO with citric acid.	43

Figure 46	FTIR spectra of UV-curable coating composed of ELO and triarylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate salts (mixed) photo initiator before and after curing.	43
Figure 47	FTIR spectra of UV-curable coating composed of ELO and bis(4-methylphenyl)iodonium hexafluorophosphate photoinitiator before and after curing.	44
Figure 48	Evaluation of the performance of catalysts and hardeners for curing ELO based on five key criteria.	44

List of Tables

Table number	Title	Page
Table 1	Chemical structure and closed formula of some key fatty acids	7
Table 2	Fatty acid names and compositions of common vegetable oils	7
Table 3	Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) for the catalysts BCF and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$, at two concentrations.	13
Table 4	Tensile strength and elongation at break of the samples cured with the catalysts BCF and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at two concentrations.	16
Table 5	Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) under curing of ELO with citric acid.	23
Table 6	Reaction onset temperature (T_{onset}), maximum reaction rate temperature (T_{peak}), and reaction enthalpy (ΔH) for curing of ELO with oxalic acid.	32
Table 7	T_5 , T_{max} and residual weight at 600°C of a sample cured with oxalic acid (with a 1:1 molar ratio of epoxy to acid groups).	34
Table 8	Physical-mechanical properties of composite with 55% wt. impregnated Scots pine sawdust, 13% wt. wood fibers, and 32% wt. ELO binder with citric or oxalic acids as catalysts. Control samples with 38% wt. untreated Scots pine sawdust, 18% wt. wood fibers and 44% wt. ELO binder with the same catalysts. Standard deviations within parentheses.	36
Table 9	Chemical structures of bimolecular photo initiators used for radical polymerization.	42

Appendix

Appendix A

In order to examine the effect of the curing time on the sample with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at 0.31% wt., it was first cured at 60°C for 1-2 h, then it was maintained at 60°C for 24 h, and it was examined every two hours. The sample after 2 and 24 h is shown in [Figure A1](#). The observations indicated that almost after two hours, the polymer solidifies, and beyond that point, there's minimal change in the resulting thermoset. In terms of mechanical strength, no significant differences occur, and only a slight color change is observed. Therefore, maintaining the polymer at 60°C after two hours, or more precisely after solidification, doesn't have a major effect on it, and this conclusion was later validated through DSC Test.

Figure A1. Sample cured with 0.31 wt. % $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ after 2 h at 60°C (a) and 24 h at 60°C (b).

To investigate the effect of temperature on the curing process of ELO with $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ – an effect expected to be similar to that of time, since both are kinetic parameters – a sample containing 0.31% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ was cured at 60°C for 2 h. This was compared to a sample that was cured for one hour at 60°C, followed by an additional hour at 100°C. The decision to start at 60°C rather than 100°C was made due to the high reaction rate and foaming that occur at the higher temperature. Thus, curing initially took place at 60°C to a certain extent before continuing at 100°C.

[Figure A2a](#) illustrates the sample cured for 2 h at 60°C, while [Figure A2b](#) shows the sample that underwent 1 h of curing at 60°C, followed by 1 h at 100°C. The experimental results indicate that, similar to the effect of time, increasing the temperature also has a comparable impact. There was no significant difference in the mechanical strength of the samples, and only a slight change in color was observed. It is important to note that evaluations at this stage were based on subjective observation rather than precise instrumental measurements. Once a sample met the required satisfaction criteria, it was selected for further, more detailed experiments.

Figure A2. Sample cured with 0.31% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ for 2 h at 60°C (a) and cured further for 1 h at 60°C followed by 1 h at 100°C (b).

It is desirable to perform the curing process at a lower temperature and for a shorter duration. However, increasing the catalyst concentration tends to lead to foaming. Therefore, we decided to investigate whether adjusting the process conditions could help prevent foaming.

Given that it has been suggested that foaming may occur due to the presence of solvent in the catalyst mixture, we prepared a sample in which the solvent was removed by applying a vacuum for 15 min prior to curing. The sample was then cured at 60°C and compared with a sample that contained the solvent. Both samples exhibited

foaming, indicating that the cause of foaming is likely related to a phenomenon other than solvent evaporation (Figure A3).

Figure A3. Sample cured with 1.2% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at 60°C without application of vacuum (a) and vacuum applied for 15 min before curing (b).

In the next step, we considered that the temperature increase during the curing reaction and thermal degradation could contribute to foaming in the samples. To improve heat transfer and reduce excessive temperature rises during the curing process, we added more solvent to the samples. Adding solvent initially can help lower the viscosity of the reacting mixture, and its subsequent evaporation can also mitigate excessive temperature increases. Consequently, we prepared samples with solvent amounts that were two, four, eight, and finally sixteen times the normal quantity.

Based on our observations (Figure A4), increasing the solvent amount improved heat transfer and reduced the temperature during the curing process, which in turn resulted in less foaming in the samples. Notably, in the sample with sixteen times the additional solvent, foaming was effectively controlled. However, it is important to highlight that this level of solvent contradicts our goal of maintaining an environmentally friendly process and material. Furthermore, despite the effective control of foaming due to the presence of solvent, the evaporation of the solvent resulted in polymers with a porous structure.

Therefore, it appears that while this approach may not be practical, we have confirmed that increased temperature and thermal degradation indeed contribute to foaming in this experiment.

Figure A4. Sample cured with 1.2% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at 60°C with solvent amounts that were two (a), four (b), eight (c), and sixteen (d) times the normal quantity.

In the next step, an attempt was made to reduce the sharp temperature rise in the curing samples by increasing the heat transfer surface area. For this purpose, a container with twice the diameter of the previous ones was used, and one-fifth of the previous sample mass was applied. Consequently, the heat transfer surface area increased fourfold, while the amount of heat generated by the reaction, which is proportional to the sample mass, was reduced to one-fifth. However, as shown in Figure 5A, thermal degradation still occurred, leading to the formation of a foam-like final product.

Figure A5. Sample cured with 1.2% wt $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at 60°C in a larger container using one-fifth of the total mass of the previous reacting mixture.

From the point that the catalyst solution would undergo a marked color change after one to two days, it was supposed that the catalyst might be changing its nature and perhaps this change in nature leads to disturbances in polymerization and the formation of foam in the samples. Therefore, an experiment was conducted to investigate the impact of this color change in the catalyst, which might be related to a change in the nature of it. The freshly prepared catalyst solution alongside the catalyst solution after two days is shown in [Figure A6](#), and the color change in these samples is clearly evident.

Figure A6. 50g/L solutions of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ after preparation (right) and after two days (left).

Samples with 1.2% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ that were freshly prepared and those that were prepared two days ago were prepared and cured at 60°C for two hours. The result was identical: using the fresh catalyst solution and the catalyst solution after two days both led to the same foam formation in the samples ([Figure A7](#)). Therefore, this color change cannot alter the catalytic nature of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$. Identical steps were repeated with BCF catalyst.

Figure A7. Sample cured with 1.2% wt. $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ at 60°C using freshly prepared catalyst solution (a) and catalyst prepared two days earlier (b).

Appendix B

Since maleic anhydride melts at 53°C , it was decided to eliminate the use of acetone as a solvent. Instead of dissolving maleic anhydride in acetone and adding the solution to ELO, ELO was first heated to 60°C , and maleic anhydride was added directly. In this way, the maleic anhydride melts in the ELO and disperses uniformly, eliminating the need for a solvent.

For this purpose, 10% wt. maleic anhydride was added to ELO at 60°C and stirred for 15 min to ensure that the solid maleic anhydride particles fully melted and dispersed uniformly in the ELO. The prepared sample was then cured at 110°C for 1.5 h. An image of this sample is shown in [Figure B1](#). The sample prepared without solvent showed little difference compared to the solvent-based sample, being only slightly more rigid. This may be due to a small amount of solvent being trapped in the polymer matrix of the solvent-based sample. Acetone can act as a plasticizer, slightly reducing the rigidity of the polymer. Therefore, maleic anhydride not only provides favorable curing temperature and time but also eliminates the need for using a solvent entirely.

Figure B1. Sample cured with 10% wt. maleic anhydride at 110°C . Maleic anhydride was directly added to ELO.

Literature studies have shown that the use of imidazole as a catalyst, in combination with carboxylic acid-based hardeners (including anhydrides) or amine-based hardeners, can enhance their reactivity. Therefore, in this experiment, maleic anhydride was used together with 2% wt. imidazole. Imidazole is a heterocyclic compound containing one tertiary amine group and one secondary amine group, and its chemical structure is shown in [Figure B2a](#).

For this purpose, imidazole was first added to ELO and stirred for 30 minutes. Then, solid maleic anhydride particles were introduced into the mixture, and stirring was continued for an additional 15 minutes at 60°C . The prepared mixture was then placed at 110°C , and after approximately 30 minutes, it was observed that the sample had turned into a foam-like structure. This phenomenon likely indicates a high reaction rate, excessive heat generation, and subsequent thermal degradation of the material (see the explanations related to the $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalyst in Appendix A). [Figure B2B](#) shows the sample.

Figure B2. Chemical structure of imidazole (a) and a sample cured with 10% wt. maleic anhydride with addition of 2% wt. imidazole at 110°C .

Since imidazole is an amine-containing compound, and it is known that amines can act as hardeners by reacting with epoxy groups (see the discussion related to diphenylamine), a new experiment was designed to determine

whether the observed increase in reaction rate in the sample containing 10% wt. maleic anhydride and 2% wt. imidazole was due to the catalytic effect of imidazole or its hardening reaction with the epoxy groups of ELO.

A sample containing only 2% wt. imidazole was prepared and kept at 110°C for 20 h. However, even after being kept at 110°C for 20 h, the mixture remained in liquid form (Figure B3a). This finding indicates that imidazole acts as a catalyst in the presence of maleic anhydride and does not independently participate in the epoxy ring-opening reaction.

Figure B3. Sample containing 2% wt. imidazole after 2 h at 110°C (a) and a sample cured with 10% wt. maleic anhydride with addition of 2% wt. imidazole at 60°C (b).

Reducing the curing temperature from 110 to 60°C prevented foam formation in the sample containing 10% wt. maleic anhydride and 2% wt. imidazole. This finding indicates that the presence of imidazole significantly lowers the curing temperature; however, the resulting polymer remained flexible and rubber-like in nature (Figure B3b).

Appendix C

To further compare the characteristics and performance of ELO and ESO, their FTIR spectra were measured and evaluated side by side. The FTIR results in the range of 4000-450 cm^{-1} are shown in Figure C1. Since the main difference between ELO and ESO lies in the number of epoxy groups, it can be observed that the peak corresponding to the epoxy groups at 821 cm^{-1} is noticeably more intense for ELO than for ESO. This confirms, consistent with the literature, that ESO indeed contains fewer epoxy groups than ELO.

It is worth noting that because ELO and ESO are both oils containing fatty acids of approximately the same chain length, their FTIR spectra are otherwise similar; for example, the triglyceride ester peak and the methylene group peaks appear essentially the same in both spectra.

Figure C1. FTIR spectra of pure ESO and ELO.

To examine whether the lower number of epoxy groups in ESO truly affects the properties of the final composite, a composite analogous to the one shown in [Figure 34](#) was produced using ESO. All preparation, molding, curing conditions, and composition were identical to the composite shown in [Figure 34](#), except that ESO was used instead of ELO. The final composite is presented in [Figure C2](#). As can be seen, this composite lacks an integrated structure and does not exhibit satisfactory mechanical strength; it could barely maintain its form. This observation demonstrates that the number of epoxy groups on the epoxidized vegetable oil is a decisive factor in determining the properties of the resulting thermoset and composite.

Figure C2. A composite consisted of 55% wt. impregnated Scots pine particles, 13% wt. wood fibres, and 32% wt. binder (ESO and citric acid).